

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D2.4

Consolidated outcome of the HARPERS project

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Executive Summary

The 3-year Euratom project, “*HARPERS: HARmonised PracticEs, Regulations and Standards in waste management and decommissioning*,” aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added value of more aligned practices and methodologies in decommissioning and radioactive waste management. Specifically, regarding i) **cross border activities** (possibilities for shared processing, storage and disposal facilities between Member States), ii) moving towards **circular economy**, iii) harmonisation and implementation of **advanced technologies** in decommissioning and waste management.

It identified the obstacles and issues preventing implementation of a more common regulatory approach, covering aspects as nuclear & industrial safety, occupational health, environmental, ...

Through a gap analysis and intensive interactions with stakeholders, nine priority topics of high interest were identified:

Cross border activities

- Harmonisation of individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory
- To align waste with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders
- Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs

Circular economy

- National regulations and criteria for clearance
- Benchmarking of circular economy approaches and technologies
- Sustainability assessment

Advanced technologies

- Standardising approaches to technology assessment and qualification for decontamination, environmental restoration, waste treatment and immobilisation
- Standardising protocols and systems to support adoption of robotics and automation in decommissioning, dismantling and waste management
- Standardising Digital Twin (DT) and Advanced Building Information Management technology and their application

A deeper analysis was performed on obstacles/issues, opportunities for more aligned practices/methodologies/approaches and their benefits & impacts. To steer the analysis, the following categories were considered: Technological, Environmental/regulatory, Commercial/economic, Operational, (socio-)Political (further abbreviated as T-E-C-O-P).

The collected data and outcome have been summarised in

- i) *Position Papers* with recommendations towards policy makers
- ii) *Business Cases* where we highlight the potential benefits of harmonisation practices compared to a base line (current existing situations).

This report consolidates the position papers and business cases and is complemented with a report [D6.1 Regulatory framework and criteria report](#)¹ which consolidates insights and analysis focused on regulatory aspects only.

This report consists of 5 main chapters. The introduction (chapter 1) briefly discusses the general challenges, related to decommissioning and radioactive waste management linked with the three themes (cross border activities/circular economy/advanced technologies). Chapter 2 describes the current state of application while the challenges and opportunities derived from a deeper analysis with stakeholders in the HARPERS project are discussed in chapter 3. Chapter 4 concludes with a set of recommendations towards harmonization at European level. The final

¹ HYPERLINK "<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/news-events/news/harpers-regulatory-framework-and-criteria-report-is-online.html>"<https://www.harpers-h2020.eu/news-events/news/harpers-regulatory-framework-and-criteria-report-is-online.html>

chapter 5 presents business cases that complement the recommendations highlighting “the case for change” together with an analysis of the benefits and impacts.

The main outcome of the project is a set of recommendations towards harmonisation which aim to inform (future) Strategic Research Agendas and policy makers. The recommendations for the three different themes are:

Cross border activities:

- Ensure that MS’s legislation allows the radioactive waste export for processing, or the import of, other countries' radioactive waste for processing and conditioning, mirrored with legislation for retrieval of secondary waste after treatment.
- Resolution of the regulatory conflicts at a National and European level regarding waste which is both radioactive and hazardous.
- Establish a European platform showcasing all European infrastructure available.
- Ensure that waste management techniques are sufficiently demonstrated for regulators/ waste owners and that there is a suitable forum for sharing information.
- Ensure that all MS’s agree the definition of problematic waste and that it is included within the individual MS legislation.
- Develop Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) for all types of waste to allow for final disposal.
- Create a legislative definition of problematic waste as this is currently missing in a majority of EU countries.
- Define European wide Best Available Technology (BAT) approach for waste characterisation and treatment. European wide agreed approaches may incentivise cross border facilities and services.
- For the radioactive hazardous waste groups (mercury, asbestos and lead), the capability to treat and dispose of these wastes was not uniformly available, so the development and utilisation of cross-border solutions could provide a means of overcoming current barriers to the management of these wastes.
- There appears to be a strong case for enhanced recycling / reuse of radiologically contaminated lead wastes, noting that there is expected to be future demand for this material (SMR/AMR).

Moving towards circular economy:

- Establish a European task force or working group to focus on harmonizing regulations for the conditional and unconditional release of materials
- Develop European technical guidelines based on best practices.
- Implement a centralized database for material release, recycling and reuse cases.
- Pilot cross-border harmonization projects.

- Foster research collaboration and Innovation, encouraging collaborative research initiatives on innovative decontamination and material characterization technologies.
- Promote public and stakeholder engagement to increase transparency, public understanding and trust in the reuse of decommissioned materials.
- Standardized training and certification programs
- Legislative roadmap with phased implementation for regulatory harmonization, starting with simpler materials and progressing to more complex cases.

Adoption of advanced technologies in decommissioning and waste management

- Establish European working group(s) for common challenges.
- Develop common guidelines and identification of good practices.
- Creation and maintenance of a centralised knowledge database.
- Cross border harmonisation of test facilities.
- Standardised training and certification programmes.

Next to the identification of obstacles and issues that may hamper more aligned methodologies and approaches and formulating recommendations as to how to overcome them, the HARPERS project also developed “Business Cases” (following the Five Case Model) in which “Cases for Change” are proposed that show the potential benefit of the change compared to a base case.

These business cases (BC) provide stakeholders/decision makers evidence related to the “case for change” to support decision making towards (future) Strategic Research Agenda’s.

Within the business cases we describe what is suboptimal about the present situation and if we do things different, what might be the benefit. The benefits/impacts are structured along the T-E-C-O-P categories (Technological, Environmental/regulatory, Commercial/economic, Operational and socio-Political).

In the HARPERS project we focused on “strategic cases” where the focus is on i) why action is needed, ii) what are the potential benefits and iii) what needs to be done to develop the BC to a point a decision for implementation can be made. Where possible we provided “economic cases” where an option assessment is given.

For the three different themes considered in HARPERS, the business cases are:

Cross border activities:

- Case for change 1: Harmonisation/Standardisation of radioactive and hazardous waste definitions.
- Case for change 2: Europe to adopt a European wide and well-defined Best Available Technology (BAT) approach for waste characterisation and treatment based on established practices and new approaches.
- Case for change 3: Reducing the stocks of legacy/historical radioactive waste in Europe by co-founded centralized treatment facilities.
- Case for change 4: Utilisation of cross-border treatment options for radiologically-contaminated hazardous wastes.
- Case for change 5: Generate a set of standard Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC), standardised packages etc. for new disposal facilities in Europe.

Moving towards circular economy:

- Business Case 1: On-site disposal of concrete.
- Business Case 2: Recycling of concrete.
- Business Case 3: Recycling of steel.
- Business Case 4: Recycling of copper and aluminium cables.

Adoption of advanced technologies in decommissioning and waste management:

A structured framework approach was proposed to help developing economic business cases for emerging technologies and subsequently tested.

- Economic case for innovative waste management and decontamination technologies.
- Economic case for robotics and automation.
- Economic case for Digital Twins and Advanced BIM technology.

By prioritising harmonisation and better alignment of practices in the areas of cross border activities, circular economy and advanced technology, the HARPERS project provided clear recommendations and proposed useful business cases towards policy makers to help remove systemic barriers and enable transformative advancements in the field of nuclear decommissioning and waste management.

1 Introduction – Nuclear industry and challenges

Since the 1950s the generation of nuclear energy has played a pivotal role in supporting the energy needs of European Union (EU) Member States (MS). With its potential to provide a stable and low-carbon energy supply, nuclear power contributes significantly to the EU's broader energy transition and climate goals. However, alongside its advantages, nuclear energy production inevitably results in the creation of radioactive waste and materials for which the safe management is a challenging task.

Nuclear waste management encompasses all activities associated with handling, treating, storing, and disposing of radioactive materials generated at various stages of the nuclear fuel cycle. These materials range from low-level waste, such as contaminated tools and clothing, to high-level waste, primarily spent nuclear fuel. The safe management of each category presents unique technical, logistical, and societal challenges, necessitating tailored solutions.

As of 2023, around 200 power reactors have been shut down worldwide, of which around 20 have already been successfully decommissioned. In addition, around 450 research reactors and more than 150 other nuclear fuel cycle facilities have already been decommissioned. By the year 2050, it is expected that more than 200 power reactors, around 220 research reactors and more than 350 fuel cycle facilities will be permanently shut down [1].

An inventory of approximately 6.5 million cubic meters of radioactive waste is reported to exist world-wide [2], all of which will need to be stored, processed, reused/recycled and disposed of in accordance with the waste hierarchy (Figure 1).

Waste hierarchy

Preventing waste is the preferred option, and sending waste to landfill should be the last resort.

Figure 1: The Waste Framework Directive (https://environment.ec.europa.eu/topics/waste-and-recycling/waste-framework-directive_en).

Around 86% of existing radioactive waste has very low level (VLLW) or low-level (LLW) radioactivity, while about ~14% is intermediate level waste (ILW) and less than 1% is high-level waste (HLW). As set out by IAEA guidance [3], all VLLW and LLW is suitable for disposal in (engineered) near-surface facilities, whereas (long-lived) ILW and HLW requires disposal at greater depths or – as the generally recognised option for HLW and SNF – in highly engineered deep geological disposal facilities (GDFs). As experience indicates, the technical, financial and political challenges of constructing a GDF are complex. In general, the storage volume of such GDFs will be limited and, consequently, efforts need to be maximised to reduce the volume of waste being sentenced to GDFs and to use the available space as efficiently as possible.

Current practices take decommissioning into account during the design phase of a nuclear facility to prevent and minimise the generation of waste at the source, e. g. by requiring a Preliminary Decommissioning Plan for nuclear new builds. However, historically, decommissioning and waste management received less consideration and has resulted in the generation of a complex and diverse nuclear waste inventory across Europe and worldwide.

In the European context, the diversity among MS in terms of nuclear power reliance and waste management infrastructure underscores the importance of a unified yet flexible approach. While countries such as Finland, France and Sweden have advanced systems for nuclear waste storage and disposal, others rely on shared expertise and collaborative frameworks. The EU's policy on nuclear waste management is guided by the 2011 Radioactive Waste and Spent Fuel Management Directive [4], which establishes a legal framework for safe and sustainable waste handling across all MS. This directive emphasizes national responsibility, transparency, and long-term solutions such as geological disposal.

Cross-border waste treatment has emerged as a critical component of the EU's nuclear waste management strategy. In cases where MS lack the necessary facilities for processing certain types of radioactive waste, they may collaborate with neighbouring countries that possess more advanced infrastructure. This practice not only optimizes the use of existing resources but also fosters solidarity and shared responsibility within the EU. However, such arrangements require rigorous regulatory oversight and clear agreements to ensure safety, equity, and adherence to international standards.

By prioritising **resource recovery**, the development of innovative decontamination techniques and/or material reuse, the nuclear industry could reduce the volume of waste to be disposed of, while also conserving valuable resources. This approach also aligns with UN sustainability goals, specifically the UN's sustainability goals twelve (responsible consumption and production) and thirteen (climate action).

The largest volume waste categories are LLW & VLLW, which must be appropriately managed, ensuring nuclear safety and radiological protection standards are implemented. At the same moment, one must consider the potential for recovering valuable materials and the need to reduce the quantity of waste and thus to minimize the environmental footprint.

The integration of **circular economy** principles into radioactive waste and material management offers a way to address these challenges.

Public engagement and trust are crucial elements of nuclear waste management strategies. Across Europe, governments and nuclear operators work to involve local

communities in decision-making processes, particularly regarding the siting of long-term storage facilities. Robust scientific research, coupled with transparent communication, helps in building confidence in the safety and reliability of these measures.

As Europe advances its clean energy ambitions, the sustainable and secure management of nuclear waste will remain a cornerstone of nuclear energy policy. By fostering international collaboration, investing in innovative technologies, and prioritizing environmental stewardship, European MS aim to set a global standard for responsible nuclear waste management.

1.1 Cross border activities – challenges and potential benefits

It is well recognized that Radioactive Waste Management should follow the principles of the Waste Framework Directive (Figure 1). This in turn, supports the application of Cross Border Waste Management to bring benefits to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management, such as minimizing waste, increasing efficiency (lower costs, and reduced risk of delays), and enhancing sustainability. Nevertheless, there are challenges ahead in implementing cross border radioactive waste management activities across Europe.

The treatment and management of nuclear waste across borders presents a complex set of challenges for EU Member States. While cross-border collaboration offers opportunities for optimizing resources and leveraging advanced infrastructure, it also raises technical, legal, and societal concerns. Addressing these challenges is essential to ensure the safety, sustainability, and efficiency of nuclear waste management within the EU.

Despite these challenges, current cross border projects such as metal recycling, incineration and high level waste transformation (making exotic uranium-compounds into stable uranium oxide), show that there are benefits to waste owners (technical and economic) as well as to the environment. They furthermore give confidence to the public that the industry is aligned to the waste hierarchy and will deal with the waste arising from legacy and decommissioning projects.

The collective understanding and experience within Europe present a significant opportunity to advance waste treatment for both simple (e.g. metal recycling) and complex waste forms (e.g. problematic waste such as resin). As technology and experience advance, academia, regulators, industry and other stakeholders are working towards the next developments, processes and solutions for a variety of wastes forms. This movement will give waste owners the opportunity to align with the waste hierarchy for their waste forms and to actually treat and reuse/dispose of waste, instead of temporarily storing it. Despite that various waste treatment/conditioning techniques already exist, application is often hampered by the local existence of small inventories, making it too costly to treat locally. In this case MS can benefit from cross border waste management activities if not hampered by regulatory aspects.

Demonstration to all stakeholders that there are adequate waste management routes available for existing as well as new build reactors (SMR's and AMR's). Failing to do so, will put a burden on the future deployment. Cross border waste management can support this growing sector and will help to provide the confidence needed to ensure successful delivery and operation.

1.2 Circular economy – challenges and potential benefits

One of the most pressing issues is the growing volume of both non-radioactive and radioactive waste generated by decommissioning and requiring to be disposed of. Radioactive waste comprises a wide range of contaminated and activated waste streams from high-level to very low-level waste (HLW to VLLW). The latter category, by far the most predominant, must be appropriately managed, ensuring nuclear safety and radiological protection standards are implemented while considering the potential for recovering valuable materials, the need to reduce the quantity of waste and to minimize environmental footprint.

It is recognized that the application of circular economy principles in nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management can lead to benefits such as minimizing waste, increasing resources efficiency or enhancing sustainability. Nevertheless, there are challenges ahead in implementing sustainability and circular economy approaches across Europe.

However, due to the lack of technological development and existing regulatory frameworks, radioactive materials which could potentially be cleared or recycled are instead considered and managed as waste.

The nuclear sector is probably among the most tightly regulated industries. These regulations are of course essential, but they can sometimes limit the development of initiatives to promote better circular economy approaches. One example is the recycling of materials with very low levels of activity, which is still prohibited under some regulations. In this respect, it would be interesting to study the need for regulatory changes to encourage more recycling projects.

When it comes to the development of circular economy initiatives, an important challenge to deal with is public perception. Indeed, the challenges of recycling very low-level waste faces reluctance from the public notably because of the issues of traceability, health and environmental impacts, etc. That's why it's important to listen to these questions and consider how best to address them.

The circular economy represents a model of production and consumption based on the efficient use of available resources in all phases; this is done by retaining assets and materials in circulation at their highest value for as long as possible, and minimizing waste, through processes like sharing, maintenance, repairing, reuse, refurbishment, remanufacturing, recovering, and recycling.

Therefore, application of circular economy principles in nuclear decommissioning is relevant both for new nuclear facilities (from the design and licensing stage) as well as for existing facilities, for instance through sharing facilities for waste processing, reuse of radioactive and non-radioactive materials and equipment, recycling of metal components, reuse of equipment parts and building materials in constructions projects, maintaining and repurposing buildings, e.g. for other industrial or medical uses.

A circular economy approach can result in decommissioning process innovation, reduced consumption of raw materials, decrease of radioactive and non-radioactive wastes generation, repurposing of facilities and/or sites, possibly lower cost and lower environmental pollution. More generally, as an economic model, circular economy can contribute to sustainability, even if existing facilities were generally designed for a

linear lifecycle, there is a great potential to align their approach to decommissioning with circularity principles.

1.3 Advanced technology – challenges and potential benefits

Experience has shown that safe decommissioning of permanently shut-down reactors and other types of nuclear facilities is generally possible with the existing technical equipment. However, there are good reasons to improve or standardise existing technical methods and to develop innovative technologies, for example to exploit optimisation potential (e.g. to reduce the radiation dose for employees, to increase process safety, to minimise secondary wastes or to reduce costs) while ensuring and improving safety and security aspects. In addition to this improvement of the status quo, new decommissioning techniques are also critical for the decommissioning of damaged reactors and some legacy sites.

Decommissioning Research and Development (R&D) is often cross-cutting and not limited to specific tasks. There are also cross-sector approaches, such as robotics or digital tools (e.g. Building Information Modelling (BIM)), which provide opportunities to optimise work and processes compared to the established practice. A mandatory prerequisite for the use of innovative technologies is a detailed proof of suitability and quality, the details of which are based in practice on the (radiological) risk potential of the application. This proof includes, for example, non-radioactive tests, radioactive laboratory-scale assessments, engineering-scale replica tests, on-plant radioactive trials and evidence of existing recovery options for technical equipment in the event of failures or risk assessments. This evidence must then be positively assessed by multiple stakeholders (e.g. the competent authority, technical experts etc.). The effort involved cannot be underestimated and, especially for those who have had no previous contact with the nuclear industry, difficult to comprehend in full detail, e.g. in terms of the required depth of testing. In addition to that, there are various further challenges that may prevent the practical use of innovative technologies. It is therefore strongly advised to analyse existing obstacles that innovative technologies are currently facing and to indicate possibilities to reduce the associated barriers without compromising safety and security.

1.4 Harpers context

The EU-project HARPERS (Harmonised practices, regulations and standards in waste management and decommissioning) has the following aims:

- a) *Identify the obstacles and issues* that could hamper the implementation of Cross border activities/circular economy principles/advanced technologies in waste management and decommissioning
- b) *Identify opportunities* for more aligned practices, methodologies and approaches across Member States (MS)
- c) *Investigate and conclude on the need and benefits* of the adoption of a more aligned approach to Cross border activities/circular economy principles/advanced technologies, to enhance waste management and decommissioning operations in Europe.

Through a gap analysis and intensive stakeholder interactions (for more details we refer to [5]), nine topics of high interest related to i) Cross Border Waste Management activities ii) Circular economy and iii) use of advanced technology in decommissioning and waste management were selected for further analysis:

Cross border activities

- Harmonisation of individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory
- To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders
- Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs

Circular economy

- National regulations and criteria for clearance
- Benchmarking of circular economy approaches and technologies
- Sustainability assessment.

Advanced technologies

- Standardising Approaches to Technology Assessment and Qualification for Decontamination, Environmental Restoration, Waste Treatment and Immobilisation
- Standardising Protocols and Systems to Support Adoption of Robotics and Automation in Decommissioning, Dismantling and Waste Management
- Standardising Digital Twin (DT) and Advanced Building Information Management Technology and their Application

A deeper analysis was performed on obstacles/issues, opportunities for more aligned practices/methodologies/approaches and their benefits & impacts. To steer the analysis, the following categories were considered: Technological, Environmental/regulatory, Commercial/economic, Operational, socio-Political (further abbreviated as T-E-C-O-P).

The collected data and outcomes have been summarised in i) Position Papers with recommendations towards policy makers and ii) Business Cases where we highlight the potential benefits of harmonisation practices compared to a base line (current situations).

This report consolidates the position papers and business cases.

In the following chapters, the report describes the current state of application (chapter 2), followed by the challenges and opportunities derived in the deeper analysis of the HARPERS project (chapter 3). Chapters 4 and 5 focus on the conclusions and recommendations and the Business Cases, respectively.

2 Application - current state

In this chapter we briefly describe the current state of application with respect to the different themes. This forms a basis towards a more detailed identification of challenges and opportunities that will be discussed in the next chapter.

2.1 Cross border activities

The current cross-border radioactive waste management activities include:

1. Shared Use of Advanced Treatment Facilities

Several EU Member States without domestic capabilities for handling certain types of radioactive waste rely on neighbouring countries with advanced treatment facilities. For example, countries such as Belgium and the Netherlands send specific categories of radioactive waste to France for processing, leveraging France's nuclear infrastructure. Several countries send metal and incinerable waste to Sweden for treatment. This has been supported by the Swedish society for decades for the treatment of others waste at Swedish waste treatment facilities, assisted by the mandatory return of the radioactive residues.

2. Collaborative Research and Development Projects

Cross-border collaboration extends to joint research initiatives aimed at improving radioactive waste treatment technologies. Programs such as the EURATOM fund research into safer and more efficient methods for processing and storing nuclear waste, with participation of multiple member states and international partners.

3. Transport and Interim Storage Agreements

Agreements between member states facilitate the transport of radioactive materials for interim storage.

There are also established waste routes between countries based on collaborations in waste treatment which last already more than 10 years. These have been developed under existing regulations and have been taking the differences into account.

The conclusion is that these actions are possible, however there is limited MS harmonization in place.

4. Regulatory and Technical Cooperation

EU member states work closely together through organizations such as the European Nuclear Safety Regulators Group (ENSREG) to harmonize safety standards and share best practices in radioactive waste management. This cooperation ensures consistency and compliance with international safety and environmental guidelines. MS set different priorities for managing nuclear waste based on political, environmental, or public concerns, however sometimes there is a lack of policy or infrastructure. Some countries may not have clear policies or sufficient infrastructure to handle waste, leading to delays or inaction.

5. Economic Considerations

Treating nuclear waste can be expensive and some countries lack the financial resources or economic justification to invest in such technologies. In addition, countries with smaller nuclear industries/inventories may not see the need to develop costly infrastructure for waste treatment if the volume of waste is relatively low.

6. Technological Capability

Some nuclear waste treatment methods require specialized technology and expertise that some countries may not possess. Also some countries rely on others to manage their waste, exporting it to nations with better-developed infrastructure.

7. Volume and Type of Nuclear Waste

Countries with extensive nuclear energy programmes, treat nuclear waste extensively because they generate large amounts. Countries with smaller nuclear industries may store waste temporarily without treatment. It should also be noted that there are differences in terminology and meanings for waste types across MS and this can also lead to inefficiency and introduce difficulties or obstacles to efficient waste treatment.

2.2 Circular economy

In a circular economy, the value of products, materials and resources is maintained for as long as possible, and the generation of waste is minimized. Implementing the waste management hierarchy is one way to promote a circular economy. In practice, it can be achieved in several ways during decommissioning of nuclear facilities or in relation to radioactive waste and materials management. From the least to the most favourable option, the waste management hierarchy considers processes to reduce (minimize the amount of waste produced), reuse (use materials more than once), recycle (use materials to make new products), recover (recover energy and metals from waste) and dispose (safe disposal of waste).

In the United Kingdom, optimisation of waste management and a requirement to follow waste hierarchy principles is a regulatory requirement for nuclear licensees responsible for waste management and nuclear facility decommissioning. The nuclear decommissioning authority (NDA) accepted in 2019 a strategic change to the Trawsfynydd site end state. The new strategy allows the operator, Nuclear Restoration Services (NRS), to consider on-site disposal of radioactive materials and waste. The new strategy was supported by a multicriteria assessment based on the NDA value framework [6], which considered various human health and environmental protection-related indicators. Such an exercise proved to be a useful way to engage with local stakeholders. Comparing different options highlighted that on-site disposal would lead to a reduction of radioactive waste volume to be disposed elsewhere, and associated minimisation of local disturbance and safety (owing to the reduction in road transport) and costs. It also reduced the amount of material needed to fill excavated areas.

In Sweden, recycling of slightly contaminated metals is a well-established practice which has been performed for almost four decades. The Czech operators of Temelin and Dukovany nuclear power plants relied on Cyclife facilities in Sweden for metal recycling. Such a practice has been recently considered in France (following a change in the regulatory framework) to reduce the amount of waste to be disposed in the CIREs disposal facility.

As outlined by Belgium R&D activities related to low carbon concrete, contaminated concrete can also be reused and even recycled. Also related to concrete, ANDRA has

R&D activities on-going aiming at reusing slightly contaminated concrete as an infill material in radioactive waste disposal facilities.

Recovery of valuable materials such as copper from slightly contaminated electric cables also fits with circular economy approaches, as outlined by Czech nuclear licensees' practices. This approach was also investigated by ANDRA (Orcade R&D project). In the Czech Republic, slightly contaminated oil and plastic are recovered for heat production.

As outlined in the Italian case study at the Casaccia site, refurbishing and repurposing of buildings (instead of new build) in the frame of a decommissioning project, is an effective approach to reducing material consumption. Considering repurposing a sustainable approach (energy efficiency, highly reliable equipment, etc.) also provides valuable benefits from a circular economy perspective.

Applying circular economy approaches and the waste management hierarchy is possible, while maintaining the highest nuclear safety and radiological protection standards. But it often requires regulatory flexibility, as outlined by case studies in the United Kingdom or France for instance. Decommissioning and radioactive waste and material management strategies are indeed strongly influenced by national contexts and regulations. Regulatory requirements should be commensurate to the level of risk.

Case studies show that innovative approaches can be considered with (sometimes) adequate evolution of the regulatory framework, and when supported by dialog with stakeholders. Multicriteria analysis allowing to score different options or strategies can be a useful tool to support such a dialog.

Apart from regulatory aspects, economic aspects remain a major aspect to consider when selecting the best strategy for radioactive waste and material management, site clean-up and decommissioning.

2.3 Advanced technologies

2.3.1 Standardising Approaches to Technology Assessment and Qualification for Decontamination, Environmental Restoration, Waste Treatment and Immobilization

Various examples of advanced technologies exist, that if realized could have impactful benefits in effective waste management and decommissioning practices. However, varied challenges are experienced in the nuclear industry which hinder the development and wider application of advanced technologies. Some examples of such technologies (provided by stakeholders) are briefly highlighted below (more details in [7]):

- i. Studsvik's patented inDRUM process converts complex drummed wastes containing organics, radioisotopes, free liquids and other reactive materials into a stabilized, non-reactive residue.
- ii. UKNNL has collaborated with partners on the development of EASD (Electrochemically Assisted Surface Decontamination), a versatile technology that could be deployed for more targeted decontamination of radioactive hotspots, which could in turn reduce metallic ILW volumes.
- iii. Cyclife's Centraco melting unit treats galvanized steel waste contaminated with short-lived low-to-intermediate-level isotopes and provides an optimized disposal route that reduces the challenge for disposal sites (e.g. gas generation related to Zn coating).

2.3.2 Standardising Protocols and Systems to Support Adoption of Robotics and Automation in Decommissioning, Dismantling and Waste Management

The nuclear back-end covers activities such as the planned decommissioning of nuclear facilities, the management of spent nuclear fuel (SNF), materials and radioactive wastes as well as the remediation of sites. Each of these activities require measures for which technical solutions are mandatory such as the use of robots.

In this report, a robot is considered in a broad sense as a technical, computer-based solution to perform specific tasks (e.g. cutting or performing measurements) that require the handling and/or manipulation of objects or measurement devices with or without the assistance of humans. In practical use cases, the level of automation of a robotic system can vary between remote control and autonomy.

Due to the benefits that robots can provide, different kinds of robots have been developed or adopted that fulfil the unique requirements of the nuclear sector, including:

- **Remote-controlled vehicles for inspections and monitoring:** These include mobile robots equipped with cameras and sensors to navigate and perform tasks in contaminated areas. They can be used for tasks like inspecting and mapping the condition of facilities [8][9]
- **Drones:** Equipped with radiation sensors, drones can survey large areas quickly and gather data from hard-to-reach places. They are useful for inspecting structures and monitoring radiation levels [10].
- **Stationary Manipulator Robots:** These robots have articulated arms that can perform precise tasks, such as welding, cutting, and removing radioactive materials. They are often used in difficult-to-reach areas but can also allow to improve efficiencies [11,12,13,14][15][16].
- **Crawler Robots:** These are tracked robots designed to move over rough terrain and are often used in areas with debris or unstable surfaces. They can be equipped with tools for cutting, sampling, and debris removal [17].
- **Hydraulic Robots:** These robots use hydraulic systems to handle heavy loads and perform tasks requiring significant force. They are used for lifting and moving large, heavy components.
- **Robots for cleaning and decontaminating:** Designed to remove radioactive contamination from surfaces, these robots use various methods, such as vacuuming or brushing, to clean areas safely and effectively [18][19].

In Europe, there have been several research and development (R&D) projects focusing on specific aspects related to robotics that received funding from the European Union (e.g. within the Horizon 2020 program), including:

- The RoMaNS² project (2015-2018) focused on developing advanced robotic systems capable of autonomously sorting and handling radioactive waste. [20,21]
- The CLEANDEM³ project (2021-2024) investigated the integration of radiologic sensors for primary and secondary inspection in a UGV (unmanned ground vehicle) platform. [22].

² The acronym stands for Robotic Manipulation for Nuclear Sort and Segregation

³ The acronym stands for Cyber physical Equipment for unmanNed Nuclear DEcommissioning Measurements

- The ongoing DORADO⁴ project (2024-2027) aims to improve safety and efficiency in nuclear decommissioning by applying digital technologies such as AI and BIM [23,24].
- The ongoing XS-Ability project (2024-2027) aims to develop robotic solutions that use sensors to cost-effectively investigate hard-to-access areas and characterize difficult-to-measure radionuclides [25]

⁴ The acronym stands for Digital twins and Ontology for Robot Assisted Decommissioning Operations

2.3.3 Standardising Digital Twin and Advanced Building Information Management

The current status of digital twin solutions in the nuclear back end reflects a cautious but growing interest in their application, albeit with notable challenges and slower adoption compared to other industries.

Digital twin technology is being explored primarily for its potential to enhance operational efficiency, safety, and predictive maintenance within nuclear facilities. However, the implementation of digital twins in the nuclear sector is still in its nascent stages. The U.S. Nuclear Regulatory Commission (NRC) has initiated research projects to evaluate the regulatory viability of digital twins for nuclear power plants. This includes understanding the current state of digital twin technology, identifying technical issues, and developing infrastructure to support regulatory decisions. The NRC has recognized that digital twins can improve operational efficiencies and safety, but significant gaps remain in integrating these technologies into existing frameworks [26].

In practical applications, digital twins are being utilized for various purposes within the nuclear industry. For instance, they are employed in reactor design and operation to simulate different scenarios, optimize performance, and predict component failures. This predictive capability is crucial for reducing the likelihood of accidents and unplanned outages. Additionally, digital twins are being applied in waste management to simulate storage and transport scenarios, thereby identifying safety hazards and optimizing management practices. In decommissioning efforts, they help simulate dismantling processes and assess potential risks [27].

Specific projects illustrate the ongoing efforts to leverage digital twin technology in nuclear operations. For example, EDF is developing digital twins for turbo generators within their nuclear power plants to validate performance before broader market implementation. This initiative aims to create configurable templates for various components across their facilities [28]. Similarly, Siemens has proposed a comprehensive digital twin methodology for modular reactors that could significantly reduce design cycles and testing costs associated with licensing new technologies.

Despite these advancements, several challenges hinder widespread adoption. Data management remains a critical issue; accurate and up-to-date data is essential for

effective digital twin simulations. The highly regulated nature of the nuclear industry complicates data sharing due to security concerns. Additionally, the expertise required to develop and maintain digital twins presents a barrier to their implementation [29].

Overall, while the potential for digital twins in the nuclear back end is recognized, their adoption lags behind other sectors due to regulatory complexities and technical challenges. Continued research and collaboration among stakeholders are necessary to bridge these gaps and fully realize the benefits of digital twin technology in enhancing safety, efficiency, and reliability in nuclear operations [30].

While BIM has gained significant traction in the broader construction industry, its adoption in the nuclear sector, particularly in back-end operations, is still in the early stages of development and implementation. One of the primary applications of BIM in the nuclear back-end is in the decommissioning of nuclear facilities by enabling improved planning and implementation [31]. BIM allows for enhanced visualization of decommissioning scenarios, benefiting both operators and external stakeholders. This improved visualization can lead to more efficient project management and better decision-making throughout the decommissioning process [32]. For instance, at the Fessenheim nuclear reactor in France [33], automated BIM modelling technologies coupled with building point clouds were used to create a static DT, which proved crucial in preparing for future dismantling operations. Another example was demonstrated in the UK via the use of the REBIM® common data environment (CDE) at Sellafield [34], where it has been employed to demonstrate the potential for future-proofing the Operations and Maintenance (O&M) phase of a new flask maintenance facility supporting nuclear decommissioning. These examples showcase the practical application of DTs and BIM in nuclear decommissioning and waste management.

BIM's potential in the nuclear back-end extends beyond decommissioning. It can also be applied to the management of spent nuclear fuel and radioactive waste. With the global inventory of spent nuclear fuel reaching around 320,000 tons of heavy metal and accumulating at a rate of approximately 7,000 tons per year [31], efficient management of these materials is crucial. BIM can assist in the planning and design of storage facilities, as well as in the tracking and monitoring of radioactive materials

throughout their lifecycle. The integration of BIM with other emerging technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning (ML), and blockchain is opening up new possibilities in the nuclear back-end.

However, it's important to note that the implementation of BIM in the nuclear back-end faces several challenges. These include the need for specialized expertise, concerns about data security, and the complexities of integrating BIM with existing systems and processes in the highly regulated nuclear industry. Additionally, the long timescales involved in nuclear back-end operations, which can span decades or even centuries, pose unique challenges for BIM implementation and data management [26].

3 HARPERS Identified Challenges and Opportunities

Through a gap analysis and intensive stakeholder interactions, the HARPERS project identified a short list of nine topics of high interest [see also section 1.4] within the three themes i) Cross Border activities ii) Circular economy and iii) Use of advanced technology in decommissioning and waste management.

In the following subchapters, the prioritised topics per theme are discussed and further analysed. A deeper analysis was performed on obstacles/issues, opportunities for more aligned practices/methodologies/approaches and their benefits & impacts. To steer the analysis, the following categories were considered: Technological, Environmental/regulatory, Commercial/economic, Operational, socio-Political (further abbreviated as T-E-C-O-P).

3.1 Cross border activities – identified challenges and opportunities

Cross border radioactive waste management related activities present both challenges and opportunities. This section explores for the three selected subtopics the potential benefits and impacts of these activities, addressing both technical and regulatory aspects. It considers the complexities associated with implementation of such activities, highlighting opportunities for innovation and requirements for regulatory evolution. It provides a comprehensive overview of possible pathways to promote and implement more efficient cross border waste management approaches in Europe.

The following priority topics were identified and were subject to more in-depth analysis:

- Harmonisation of individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory
- To align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders
- Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs

The identified challenges and opportunities are described here, more details can be found in the position paper [35].

3.1.1 Harmonisation of Individual EU and international countries problematic waste inventory

Level of Cross-border Cooperation and Partnerships in Radiactive waste (RAW) Challenges

The majority of European countries consider the NPPs as the primary source of radioactive waste in their country and have collaborations or partnerships with other organizations or regulatory bodies to address radioactive waste management challenges in general and cross border cooperation. European projects provide a basis for collaborations regarding the RAW classification system. Except for European projects, also the active participation and follow up of international centres for cooperation (IAEA, NEA/OECD, nucleareurope and World Nuclear Association) in the nuclear field is crucial and applied by European countries.

An example of a good practice within a country, is the UK with the Problematic Waste Integrated Project Team (PW IPT), which facilitates communication and sharing of experience between problematic waste-owning organisations. This helps waste owners to progress in the management of problematic waste types on their sites. The PW IPT is also looking to involve representatives of nuclear new builds and small modular reactors (SMRs), with the aim of helping these industries prevent the generation of problematic wastes in future.

Other European countries not only give attention to the challenges of RAW classification, definition of problematic waste (PW), inventory of existing “problematic” waste (according to their current definition/understanding of PW), but they also forecast and identify the PW to be generated in the future. For example, Romania anticipates activated lead and waste contaminated with lead or polonium to be generated by operation of the ALFRED facility at RATEN ICN site.

Optimization of RAW management practices is a continuous cyclic process, and enhancement of cross-border cooperation should have a permanent position in the European forum discussions.

Problematic waste

Although all MS have problematic waste, only limited number of MS (e.g. UK, France) have an internal (within organization) unified definition for problematic wastes ensuring alignment across departments or stakeholders involved in waste management processes. Therefore, it may be concluded that most of the organizations are waiting for national/international legislation or the world's centres for cooperation in the nuclear field to come to a unified definition for problematic waste.

The experience of respondents that are managing problematic waste, confirm that it is challenging and complex due to i) demanding nature in terms of technical level of detail, ii) time and cost; iii) interfaces with stakeholders (WM operators, Regulators, Public, etc.); iv) unavailability of waste management route and related guidelines on problematic waste WAC (only guidelines for WACs for standard waste is available).

European countries are actively addressing the issue of the “problematic waste” which is confirmed by the fact that seven out of ten respondents stated that they have plans or experience/solutions applicable for problematic waste in their country. The respondents are searching mainly for the solutions and developing plans for that type of problematic waste, which they have as the problematic waste generated within their country, as it is their responsibility.

Waste classification system in context of Cross Border Cooperation

In terms of waste classification European countries implement the EU directives, or international recommendations for waste classification (e.g. IAEA's Safety Standards Series No. GSG-1/2009; EC council directive 2011/70/EURATOM). Therefore, it is necessary to address and define the “problematic waste” on this international level.

The majority of respondent countries consider the waste classification and waste management system adopted in their country supporting the cross-border cooperation. The main obstacle in terms of cross border cooperation (treatment and conditioning of waste) is therefore not the adopted waste classification and waste management system, but the fact whether the country's legislation allows the RAW export for processing or the import of other countries' RAW for processing and conditioning.

A harmonized radioactive waste classification system across all EC Member States may help to improve cross border cooperation, but it is not a main driver for the improvement of cross-border cooperation. The cross-border cooperation in terms of RAW treatment and conditioning, is a result of international tendering with the result based on quality (technologies is the country providing services, extent of minimization of the volume of RAW, etc.) and price (economic efficiency, distance between the countries).

Harmonisation (alignment) of the RAW Classification across EU MS

Even if a majority of EU MS consider the potential harmonization of RAW classification system as beneficial, there are concerns regarding the joint development of the system and the level of the strictness of the harmonized RAW classification system.

The benefits of harmonized RAW classification system are understood mainly as easier comparison, benchmarking and exchange of information on RAW management practices within Europe. Nevertheless, there are other expected benefits for example, facilitating using existing processing facilities across Europe; paving the way towards a harmonized international waste processing and disposal system.

Majority of Respondents' countries has legislation to cover the export/import of radioactive waste to or from other EU Member State; however there is room for improvement.

The main challenges in harmonizing and achieving consistency in waste inventories and achieving consistency in the reporting and management of hazardous waste between individual EU members are: i) differences in definition of “problematic” vs “hazardous” waste; ii) the common definition of the problematic waste should be robust (not omitting any of the specific “problematic” wastes which the countries have or expect to have in the future); iii) issue of sharing sensitive information; iv) misalignment of waste categorisation; v) issue of acceptance of the common system by respective countries; vi) necessity of demonstration of benefits to stakeholders; vii) necessity of addressing the specific or general exemption levels, etc.

3.1.2 Align wastes with treatment technologies in a manner acceptable to all stakeholders

Importance of waste treatment

The data gathered demonstrates the alignment, and the application of the Waste Hierarchy, noting that there are several criteria which drive decisions (e.g. quantities, shape & dimensions; e.g. large components or small scrap metal) as well as regulatory support and hindrance for treatment of certain waste forms. It was noted that organic waste (including resins), liquids and metals were the most important for current treatment and that other treatment processes are needed for other waste forms to go forward.

Waste Treatments available – but not used in their MS

Sometimes waste treatment technologies are available, but not used. A summary of the reasons why current treatment is not done (with examples) are shown below:

- Waste Acceptance Criteria - Bituminized wastes were noted that they could be treated, but the final disposal Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) had not been identified, so no treatment had been undertaken.
- Characterisation - Legacy waste characterisation, moreover the inability to characterise it, means that these waste forms cannot be sent for treatment and will likely be complicated to qualify for disposal.
- Inability to meet treatment criteria – Liquid organic wastes may need some pretreatment (separation of solid and liquid) before they can be sent for final treatment. However, some pretreatments can leave a secondary waste that may not have a final treatment process (e.g. liquid waste).
- Historical waste treatment processes are not practical in the current day – Evaporator wastes have previously been dried out, but current waste arisings are small, making evaporator treatment ineffective.
- Ability to free release the final product – Current treatment process for insulation material and galvanised material is a difficult and ineffective process, which does not lead to free release, so the processes are not utilised in certain MS.
- Treatment options are not efficient, or create a larger volume, after treatment – Resins cannot be efficiently treated in certain MS, and that the only main option is grouting. Some can be incinerated in small quantities in certain MS.
- Transport restrictions or high cost is prohibitive to treatment options when waste is either uncharacterized or of some forms.

Waste Treatments that are acceptable by local stakeholders

Where waste treatments are available to the waste owners and are used, information has been obtained as to why stakeholders find the treatment process acceptable. A summary of the Stakeholder acceptance views for specific treatments (with examples) are shown below:

- Compliance with the Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) – Treatment solution is demonstrated to meet the WAC, which gives sufficient confidence to the regulator and, in applicable cases, the organisation responsible for the disposal of the residuals for disposal at the appropriate facility/repository. An example is with contaminated metals which can be decontaminated and melting where necessary, which allows the demonstration of the WAC post treatment. Please note that some WAC's have not been developed for final disposal facilities and several MS have no disposal sites, making it challenging to develop WACs, as yet.
- Regulator engagement – Dedicated and supported campaigns on specific waste types such as Lead treatment (melting) have been organized with the active engagement of regulators to ensure necessary outcome [36].
- When the stakeholders support the “Recycling and Reuse” approach, it is adopted based on a proven approach with the focus on preserving the environment. Metal treatment (all metal types) is an example of this, and stakeholders support this approach based on the demonstration of its efficiency and understanding of the process. An additional benefit from recycling and reuse of metals is the positive operational expenditure (OPEX) outcome from the treatment.
- Stakeholder defines the need to preserve and improve the environment, through the deployment of national policies within MS. Certain treatment processes support this environmental policy aim which in turn facilitates stakeholder support in waste treatment.
- Stakeholders require the waste owners/treatment facilities to demonstrate that the Best Available Techniques (BAT) are adopted and justified to meet the local regulations. Once BAT is adopted, this improves the Stakeholder endorsement of a treatment method.
- A long history of problem-free waste related activities by an organization triggers enhanced support from the local stakeholders, creating work opportunities, tax income, and is regarded as environmentally supportive.

Waste Treatments that are NOT acceptable by local stakeholders

Information and opinion gathered has also identified why certain treatments are not acceptable by stakeholders. A summary of the views raised are shown below:

- Low Technology Readiness Level (TRL) for the treatment process – Additional research and development, or proving works is needed to provide confidence to stakeholders that the proposed treatment process is sufficient.
- Local regulations do not allow for treatment due to the nature of the waste, the treatment process available or the inability to send waste to another country for treatment.
- Individual MS WAC's are not sufficient – Example: Some galvanised metals can neither be treated or disposed of in certain countries, even if they have proven metal treatment capabilities, however other MS have the ability to treat galvanised metals and wastes can be sent abroad for treatment.
- Characterization issues prevent treatment – Legacy wastes present a significant challenge for future waste treatment due to the lack of characterization data.
- Additional pretreatment of wastes (such as repacking) is required before treatment and disposal is required by stakeholders – This applies specifically to R&D and Institutional radioactive originating wastes.
- Cost of treatment is prohibitive – Stakeholders can allow the treatment of waste forms, but the cost of treatment, or the volume of waste, or the risk profile of the waste, means it's not set as a priority for treatment at this stage (such as highly contaminated steels)

Why Wastes are treated or not, and can cross border treatment provide additional options for stakeholders

The following information provides a summary as to what has been raised as to the reasons for not utilising cross border treatment:

- There are no disposal sites and thus no WACs, making treatment of waste highly uncertain as there are no guarantees that the residue after treatment can be disposed of.
- Local regulations not sufficiently developed - further development needed to see if local regulations can be adopted to send waste to another MS for treatment. Waste facilities can be identified overseas, but local regulations may hamper treatment abroad.
- Waste treatment facilities are not available in certain MS due to low waste volumes making them not economically viable
- Transportation of waste can be problematic for waste treatment in the country of origin, in transferring countries, and countries where treatment facilities are located depending on the characteristics and activity levels.
- Local waste treatment capability is not sufficient.
- The cost of treatment and transport is prohibitive – Priority may not be given to certain waste forms.

3.1.3 Member States approach to dealing with radioactive contaminated hazardous waste differs

Definition of radioactive hazardous waste, legislative context and feasibility of cross border treatment

To start, we wanted to clarify whether there was a common definition of radioactive hazardous wastes. All MS except for Denmark reported that hazardous waste definitions are based on EC legislation. Waste that is both hazardous (in their non-radioactive form) and radioactive is considered in first instance as radioactive waste, and are thus subject to the relevant radioactive waste regulations. Responses indicated that hazardous waste regulations must also be adhered to, and where these regulations conflict, the most stringent regulations take precedence. Only Italy noted the development of legislation unifying the two separate regulations. The management of radioactive hazardous waste in other countries might benefit from similar unifying legislation but the situation appears to be manageable. Reasons for the different management options available for radioactive and non-radioactive hazardous waste were reported as owing to different legislation (or their independent development) and different management concepts and needs.

Regarding the prospect of providing or utilising cross-border treatment options for the radioactive hazardous waste groups that were investigated (mercury, asbestos and lead), this appears to be feasible: all MS reported that import/export (to OECD countries) of mercury, asbestos and lead radioactive wastes for treatment is permitted, providing the treated and secondary waste is returned to the owning nation. EU regulation prohibits the export of hazardous, non-radioactive mercury to non-OECD countries. Only Czechia reported that the import of radioactive waste into its territory is prohibited (although notes an exception for treatment purposes provided the waste is returned to sender). For the radioactive hazardous waste groups that were investigated (mercury, asbestos and lead), the capability to treat and dispose of this waste is not uniformly available across responding countries, and so the development and utilisation of cross-border solutions could provide a means of overcoming barriers to the management of these wastes (more details in [35]).

3.1.4 Potential benefits and impacts

The potential benefits of Cross Border Waste Management have been identified and refined, are summarised below. The relevant aspects of these benefits have been used in the Cases for Change highlighted in the WP3 Business Case (section 5.2), and which form the basis of the conclusions and Recommendations in section 0.

1. Optimized Use of Existing Infrastructure

Cross-border nuclear waste treatment enables member states to leverage advanced facilities and technologies available in other countries. This reduces the need for individual nations to invest in costly infrastructure, particularly those with limited nuclear programs or smaller quantities of waste. Using joint BAT facilities also support a sustainable society.

2. Enhanced Safety Standards

By consolidating nuclear waste treatment in facilities with proven safety records, cross-border cooperation can enhance overall safety. Advanced facilities are often equipped with cutting-edge technologies and staffed by highly trained personnel, reducing the risks associated with waste handling and storage. This collective approach can improve safety outcomes across the region.

3. Cost Efficiency

Treating nuclear waste across borders can lead to significant cost savings for member states. Developing and maintaining national facilities for all types of nuclear waste is financially demanding, particularly for countries with limited nuclear energy programs. Sharing resources and facilities allows for economies of scale, reducing the per-unit cost of waste treatment and storage.

4. Accelerated Progress on Long-Term Solutions

Cross-border collaboration can expedite the development and implementation of long-term nuclear waste management solutions, such as deep geological repositories. By pooling financial and technical resources, member states can advance projects more efficiently, reducing delays and ensuring timely progress towards permanent disposal solutions.

5. Strengthened European Solidarity and Cooperation

Cooperating on nuclear waste treatment fosters a sense of solidarity and shared responsibility among EU member states. This collaborative approach aligns with the EU's broader goals of promoting unity and mutual support. It also helps to build trust and strengthen political and technical relationships between countries.

6. Improved Environmental Protection

Consolidating nuclear waste treatment in well-regulated, advanced facilities minimizes the environmental risks associated with improper waste handling and storage. Centralized treatment and disposal ensure that waste is managed in a manner that adheres to the highest environmental standards, reducing the potential for contamination and long-term ecological harm.

7. Knowledge Sharing and Capacity Building

Cross-border waste treatment facilitates the exchange of technical expertise and best practices between member states. Countries with less experience in nuclear waste management can benefit from the knowledge and skills of their more advanced counterparts. This not only enhances the capabilities of individual nations but also strengthens the EU's overall capacity to manage nuclear waste safely and effectively.

In summary, the cross-border treatment of nuclear waste offers numerous benefits for European member states, ranging from cost efficiency and enhanced safety to environmental protection and strengthened regional cooperation. By working together, EU countries can ensure the safe, sustainable, and effective management of radioactive materials, supporting the region's energy and environmental goals while fostering a spirit of unity and collaboration.

3.2 Circular economy – Identified challenges and opportunities

Decommissioning nuclear facilities consistently with circular economy principles presents both challenges and opportunities. This section explores the potential benefits and impacts of integrating circular economy principles into nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management, addressing both technical and regulatory aspects. It also considers the complexities associated with implementing circular economy principles in this context, highlighting opportunities for innovation, requirements for regulatory evolution, and societal acceptance. By examining case studies and ongoing research, this work aims at providing a comprehensive overview of the pathways for a more sustainable and resource-efficient approach to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management.

The following priority topics were identified and were subject to more in-depth analysis:

- National regulations and criteria for clearance
- Benchmarking of circular economy approaches and technologies
- Sustainability assessment.

The identified challenges and opportunities are described here, more details can be found in the position paper [37].

3.2.1 Challenges and limitations

At the international level, the regulation of nuclear activities is overseen by agencies such as the IAEA and the European Commission, which provide comprehensive guidelines and legal frameworks to ensure safety, security, and sustainability of nuclear operations. These bodies emphasize the importance of safeguarding human health and the environment from the potentially harmful effects of ionizing radiation. As a result, regulatory frameworks are heavily focused on the safe disposal of radioactive waste, with stringent protocols for containment, long-term storage, and disposal.

One of the primary challenges in considering circular economy aspects related to the management of radioactive waste and materials at the international level is that these regulations are predominantly designed to prevent the spread of contamination, ensure the integrity of containment systems, and minimize exposure risks. This focus on

radiological protection often undermines the principles of reuse and recycling, which involve extracting usable materials from waste and potentially reintroducing them into the production cycle. Moreover, international safety standards tend to be conservative by nature by mainly focusing on the radiation protection of the public, without paying enough attention that for very low levels of contamination the radiological risk is negligible. This is central to many radiation protection regulations, which can be a barrier to the promotion of new and potentially safer techniques for recycling or reusing radioactive materials. In particular, the issue of radioactive clearance - allowing materials to be deemed non-radioactive and returned to the economy - faces scrutiny. Achieving regulatory approval for clearance levels, where materials are deemed "safe" for reuse or recycling in non-nuclear industries, can be a protracted and contentious process, even when advancements suggest that certain materials could pose little or no risk.

At the European level, different approaches exist to radioactive waste management. The regulatory frameworks for nuclear waste disposal, recycling, and reuse may differ significantly from one country to another, creating challenges for cross-border cooperation (see also section related to cross border 3.1). Some countries have made notable progress in recycling, but challenges remain for countries who have a more conservative approach, placing greater emphasis on safe containment and long-term geological disposal.

While regulations are supposed to be based on the same EC radioactive waste directive, this heterogeneity in national regulations can impede the establishment of a unified, pan-European approach to radioactive waste management. In particular, the absence of harmonized standards for waste classification and disposal complicates efforts to implement circular economy practices across borders. To illustrate, some countries may allow the clearance of low-level radioactive materials, whereas others may limit such practices due to concerns about contamination risks or public perception. The result is an uneven playing field, where the potential benefits of recycling and reuse may be stifled by regulatory differences.

The essence of the circular economy for radioactive waste rests in the reuse and recycling of cleared materials. However, these practices face several key **regulatory challenges**:

- Clearance levels and material recycling: one of the most challenging aspects is the establishment of clearance levels - the thresholds at which materials can be removed from the regulatory oversight of radioactive waste management. While materials such as metals or concrete can theoretically be cleaned and reused in non-nuclear industries, regulatory frameworks may impose tight limits on what can be considered "safe" for reuse. The process of determining clearance levels involves complex scientific assessments and extensive characterisation, which can delay or prevent the approval of recycling programs because of too long procedures.
- Long-term liability: in some cases, countries can be reluctant to allow the reuse of radioactive materials without robust mechanism that may address future potential health or environmental issues. While these issues can, in principle, be associated with the regulatory framework (e.g., clear mechanisms for tracking the lifecycle of recycled nuclear materials), further analysis is needed to determine whether the root causes lie within the regulatory framework itself or stem from implementation practices, interpretative differences, or other structural factors. It is important to consider that the recycling economy within the nuclear industry should be promoted, considering that tracking ends once the materials have passed clearance (as it is currently applied in the case of remelted metal).

The reuse, recycling and clearance of decontaminated radioactive materials also faces various **technical challenges**:

- The first challenge is to be able to have sufficient materials that can be potentially considered for reuse or recycling so that the implementation of a decontamination operation is profitable and that customers can be interested.
- The second challenge is to be able to demonstrate that the materials concerned are well decontaminated and meet the radioactivity thresholds for declassifying these materials. This demonstration can involve measurements of very low radiological activities, which are not necessarily accessible with current measuring devices in an industrial setting (i.e. not in the laboratory). Additionally, in case of melting, it must also be demonstrated that the residual radiological level of these decontaminated materials is homogeneous in the matrix of these materials, some nuclear radiation may not be detected on the surface of these materials. The homogenous character then becomes a predominant characteristic that must be demonstrated.

The implementation of circular economy approaches in decommissioning and radioactive waste management faces also **social challenges**. Public perception towards the reuse and recycling of materials with traces of radioactivity is often affected

by the stigma surrounding the nuclear industry. Environmental sustainability should be considered as a driving factor for public acceptance and a comparative framework that allows an analysis of solutions, based on technological opportunities and regulatory frameworks, should be developed for the social demonstration of the benefits of the circular economy in comparison with the linear economy.

A guidance framework based on a Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA) has been developed (See [37 annex 6.3]) to integrate environmental, societal, and economic factors in the comparison of different alternatives. This approach promotes flexibility and dialogue, facilitates traceable decision-making and fosters collaboration among stakeholders. One of the most significant challenges in developing the framework for social evaluation is striking a balance between inclusiveness and practicality by limiting the number of criteria without compromising thoroughness. Additionally, the dynamic and context-specific nature of social factors further complicates the development of a universally applicable framework. Nevertheless, to ensure a holistic evaluation, it is common practice to begin with a broad set of criteria, which are then systematically refined to eliminate redundancies and exclude potentially irrelevant factors.

The HARPERS guidance for the sustainability assessment (See [37 annex 6.3]) was developed through several months of preparation and multiple rounds of consultation. It was further refined through Delphi analysis and expert evaluations. The importance of clearly defined objectives, criteria and quantifiable indicators was highlighted as an essential part of the methodology for the comparison of linear and circular economy, providing a better understand of the issue and a clearer identification of benefits and challenges.

3.2.2 Potential solutions and ongoing R&D

The previous paragraph highlights some of the challenges in applying circular economy principles to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste and materials management. Legislative, technical, and social obstacles demand innovative solutions to overcome these barriers and, finally, ensuring more sustainable practices.

On the legislative front, the need for greater harmonization of national practices is evident, as varying legal frameworks often hinder the efficient implementation of circular economy strategies.

A preliminary step involves exploring national regulatory boundaries and engaging with authorities through existing case studies. These studies can create precedents and clarify interpretations for future applications of circular economy principles, while also helping to identify inconsistencies in current national regulations. Examples (See [37 annex 6.2]) include the conditional release of contaminated concrete (Belgium – Tractebel) and metals (Belgium – SCK CEN; Sweden – Cyclife), as well as the release of small quantities of specific waste such as plastics, oil, and sludge (Czech Republic – Dukovany and Temelín NPPs). These studies offer insights into handling different materials and contamination levels under varied legal frameworks, providing valuable data for refining policies. Disseminating case study findings through European and international projects, such as HARPERS, can support national authorities in testing regulatory limits and provide international bodies like the IAEA with robust data to develop guidelines. Such harmonization efforts can lead to a more unified approach that benefits both regulators and industries.

Technically, optimizing characterization, segregation and treatment methods is critical for recycling dismantled materials and minimizing radioactive waste fractions. Improved techniques can significantly enhance material recovery rates while ensuring that radioactive contaminants are safely managed. Advances in measurement and characterization techniques are equally vital, as precise analysis is essential for determining whether materials meet safety standards for reuse. A better and more fundamental understanding of the various separation techniques leads to a more accurate determination of the type and quantity of materials that can be recycled, thereby reducing the amount of radioactive waste. This necessitates a range of research initiatives, from applied to fundamental studies, which explore innovative technologies and methodologies. For instance, the SMELD project (Belgium – SCK CEN [38]) explores metal melting processes to enhance radionuclide migration to slag, achieving higher decontamination factors. Similarly, ENEA (Italy) has investigated the impact of acid type and sample concentration on radiological characterisation measurements through Liquid Scintillation Counting for reaching the stringent clearance levels requested by Regulatory Authority for steel samples [39]. These efforts demonstrate how technical innovation can significantly improve recycling efficiency, reducing the environmental impact of nuclear decommissioning.

Encouraging collaborations between research institutions and operators can accelerate the development of such technologies.

The societal impact of aligning nuclear decommissioning practices with circular economy principles is profound, as public perception plays a pivotal role in the acceptance of recycled materials. Transparent dialog with stakeholders, including governments, industries, and the public, can foster trust and acceptance of such practices. Initiating targeted projects to achieve these objectives is strongly recommended, as these projects can serve as platforms for dialog and information-sharing. Additionally, educating stakeholders through new or adapted training programs focused on the unique challenges of circular economy applications in nuclear decommissioning is crucial. Such programs can help build technical expertise, increase awareness of the overall benefits of recycling, and address public concerns about radiological protection and environmental impact. Promoting these initiatives at both national and international levels can strengthen cooperation and lead to more consistent practices across countries.

3.2.3 Potential benefits and impacts

3.2.3.1 Recycling and reuse of materials

Recycling materials generated during decommissioning enables a more efficient use of available resources. Recycling of metals is a common practice within the nuclear industry. For materials where recycling is a less established practice, techniques and processes could be adapted from other industries. However, there may be some technical challenges associated with the application of these processes to radioactive materials and these processes are often more complex than direct disposal.

Recycling aligns with waste hierarchy principles, significantly reducing the demand for raw materials, energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. For instance, steel recycling mitigates the environmental impacts of ore mining, while recycling concrete avoids the need to quarry new aggregates. Recycling materials also reduces the need for disposal space. Construction and expansion of repositories use significant amounts of resources and materials.

Decontamination, clearance and recycling materials has capital and operational costs, which must be balanced against the cost benefits seen. Depending on national context, material type and volume, there may be significant benefits, such as a reduction in disposal volumes and thus a reduction in repository capacity demand. This reduction may lower costs, as some types of repository disposal are costly (e.g. geological disposal), though others are relatively cost effective (e.g., VLLW disposal at CIRES in France). Furthermore, monetising recycled materials offers a secondary revenue stream.

Recycling materials may have an impact on operational safety when compared to disposal of the same material, due to the increased complexity. However, this is outweighed by the fact that recycling avoids the need for quarrying or mining to extract new materials, which are likely to have more significant impact on operational safety.

The circular economy approach promotes recycling, addressing societal expectations for sustainability and improving public perception of nuclear decommissioning practices. However, there can be stakeholder concerns around the origin of recycled material. Experience in Sweden has shown that these concerns can be overcome with effective stakeholder dialog.

In order to realize the importance of releasing materials for the possibility of their recycling and reuse across Europe, starting from the IAEA open sources data available as well as illustrative information from some HARPERS partners, it has been estimated that within the EU (+ UK, Switzerland) up to 56 million tons of released materials (steel and concrete) from decommissioning can be generated [40], opening up the possibility that these materials can be recirculated in the near future within the EU.

3.2.3.2 Reuse of sites and infrastructures

Refurbishment and life extension of existing plants and facilities, as well as reuse of components and repurposing of buildings for waste processing and storage, including the eventual post-decommissioning use of the site, are quite related to circularity principles. The use of material from demolished buildings as bulk to fill empty spaces is also consistent with circularity.

Important experience exists in this field, some of which has been collected in the case studies presented in [37 annex 6.2]). They include examples of repurposing and

refurbishing of existing buildings to allow their use as a temporary storage facility at the Casaccia site in Italy, and a strategic change in the UK Trawsfynydd site end state to include on-site disposal of some of the radioactive waste resulting from decommissioning as an option. These case studies highlight that comprehensive planning, including multicriteria assessment of the possible options, is important to allow the identification of issues and benefits of different options, and to ensure the optimal approach is adequately considered and selected. Evolution of regulation or development of standards have been identified as enablers for a more circular approach to reuse and refurbishing. Opportunities and challenges for reuse and repurposing of facilities and sites site have also been discussed during an IAEA Technical Meeting [40].

It was recognized that optimization in the use of available resources can contribute to sustainability. Implementing circular economy principles leads to a reduction in consumption of fresh resources (materials, energy) through reuse and repurposing.

A change of frame of reference should be promoted: from considering the nuclear facility as a liability that must be removed to the recognition of the value of the existing infrastructure and the possible beneficial uses for the community (sustaining jobs, developing opportunities for local enterprises/networks, attracting new investors).

Early stakeholder engagement and transparency in the decision-making processes is necessary to communicate and share visions and benefits of circular approaches and supports trust as well as awareness and understanding of potential value and options.

Cost aspects and timescale remain key considerations, in particular where there are substantial costs incurred in the short-term but that economic and environmental benefits may only be realized or visible in the longer term.

Some suggestions have been identified, by the experts participating in the IAEA Technical Meeting, to remove barriers to reuse and repurpose nuclear facilities and sites including:

- Better alignment of key policies and drivers for implementing circular economy principles,

- Culture changes within the industry (from removing liability to shared value and beneficial uses) and the regulators (to enable and encourage more sustainable and circular decommissioning practices & facilitate repurposing/reuse options),
- Education/awareness of circular lifecycle perspectives for assets including sustainability, an integrated vision and a longer time frame perspective,
- Enhanced stakeholder engagement practices and decision making, grounded in community (shared) rather than corporate (owned) values,
- Economic considerations, including cost uncertainties and barriers,
- Sharing of experiences and lessons learned,
- Clear vision (and supporting tools), from the design stage, about design options and materials choices to facilitate reuse and repurposing.

3.3 Advanced technologies – identified challenges and opportunities

Applying advanced technologies in decommissioning and waste management presents both challenges and opportunities. This section explores potential benefits and impacts of the use of certain advanced technologies (e.g. innovative waste treatment technologies, robotics, DT, BIM) into nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management addressing both technical and regulatory aspects. It provides a comprehensive overview of possible ways to facilitate implementation and standardization of such advanced technologies.

The following priority topics were identified and were subject to more in-depth analysis:

- Standardising Approaches to Technology Assessment and Qualification for Decontamination, Environmental Restoration, Waste Treatment and Immobilisation
- Standardising Protocols and Systems to Support Adoption of Robotics and Automation in Decommissioning, Dismantling and Waste Management
- Standardising Digital Twin (DT) and Advanced Building Information Management Technology and their Application

The identified challenges and opportunities are described here, more details can be found in the position paper [41].

3.3.1 Standardising Approaches to Technology Assessment and Qualification for Decontamination, Environmental Restoration, Waste Treatment and Immobilisation

Legacy nuclear facilities frequently contain a wide range of different physical, chemical and radiological hazards which are poorly characterised, difficult to access and in turn hard to decontaminate. This can often result in people having to work hands-on in dangerous environments and operations being conducted that generate significant volumes of secondary waste. Various advanced decommissioning and waste management technologies are being developed to overcome the industry's complex challenges (examples given in [7]). However, a range of common barriers are experienced which hinder their development and wider application, including:

- A lack of detailed plant records and operational histories to baseline the scale of the challenge
- The lack of availability of clear and common treatment and disposal routes and the associated Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC)
- Limited availability of characterisation data quality objectives (DQO) and characterisation capability
- Lack of shared understanding on existing technologies and their Technology Readiness Level (TRL)
- Limited access to radioactive materials and testing facilities to demonstrate advanced technologies
- Uncertainty related to licensing, market size, operator appetite and current waste disposal/treatment method costs
- Lack of common shared assumptions for Cost Benefit Analysis

The focus was specifically on understanding how standardising approaches to technology assessment and qualification for decontamination, environmental restoration, waste treatment and immobilisation could benefit from existing and future decommissioning practices, both in Europe and globally. (A more detailed list of identified common barriers and potential solutions identified can be found in 41.

If successfully achieved, the benefits of implementing advanced technologies on a wide scale may include:

- Reduced hands-on work and radiation dose to workers
- Re-classification and volume reduction of the waste requiring near- and sub-surface disposal

- Improved options for decommissioning strategy development and safety case planning
- Deployment of faster and more efficient processes
- Processing of problematic / orphan waste streams
- Cost reductions (as a result of the above)

3.3.2 Standardising Protocols and Systems to Support Adoption of Robotics and Automation in Decommissioning, Dismantling and Waste Management

The nuclear back-end covers activities such as the planned decommissioning of nuclear facilities, the management of SNF and radioactive wastes, as well as the remediation of sites. Each of these activities requires measures for which technical solutions are mandatory. For this purpose, robots have the potential to provide added value, including:

- Reduction of operator exposures to hazardous conditions
- More efficient use of personnel
- Remote operation capabilities to allow intervention in inaccessible or dangerous areas without direct human presence
- Optimisation of the risk assessment, including safety risks and project risks
- Efficient decision making as a result of automated data collection and data analysis
- Improved asset utilisation through enhanced capabilities of robots, leading to better capital efficiency
- Reduction of operational costs due to reduced labour costs, minimised impact of human errors and automated repetitive actions/activities
- Reduction of time-consuming and recurring preparations, e.g. related to putting on personal protective equipment
- Increasing attractiveness to new generation workforces

In addition, robots are usually required for the decommissioning of complex legacy sites (e.g. Sellafield, La Hague) and complex decommissioning projects (e.g. Fukushima and Chernobyl) due to unique challenges arising from potential risks and radiation levels.

Due to the benefits that robots can provide, different kinds of robots have been developed or adopted that fulfil the unique requirements of the nuclear sector. However, despite the fundamental advantages that robots and automated systems can

provide, impediments exist that currently still limit the number of applications, especially those with a high level of automation. A thorough understanding of such barriers from different points of view is essential to find solutions that reduce these impediments without compromising safety and security. Here, it should be noted that the on-going activities of the NEA Expert Group on the Application of Robotics and Remote Systems in the Nuclear Back-end (EGRRS) include aspects such as the implementation of robotics and the analysis of certain barriers and the provision of recommendations (e. g. in terms of cost-benefit analysis) [42,43].

The strong need for reducing such barriers has also been supported by the stakeholder engagement conducted in the HARPERS project, during which certain needs have been identified, including:

- Guidance (including from regulators) and sharing experience on demonstrating safety and security to regulators (safety case), appropriate to the environment of application (basic to harsh)
- Communication routes with regulators during technology development
- Standardisation of protocols, control systems and interfaces, including standardised architecture for robotics and standards for manufacturing to support verification and validation stages
- Transfer of knowledge/technologies from other industries and sharing experience on evaluation and use of robotics on sites, for different applications
- Evaluate new procedures/protocols to integrate automation and robots or drones in the nuclear environment (e.g. Indoor use of unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV))
- Internationally aligned practices

We considered the barriers that impede the use of robotics in the nuclear back-end and provided selected recommendations – with a special attention to standardisation – that may lead to a reduction of such barriers. A more detailed list of identified common barriers and potential solutions can be found in [41]).

3.3.3 Standardising Digital Twin and Advanced Building Information Management

The nuclear industry, particularly in its back-end operations, is increasingly recognising the need for digitalisation to enhance efficiency, safety, and cost-effectiveness. As nuclear facilities age and decommissioning becomes a pressing concern, digital technologies offer innovative solutions to complex challenges. DTs and BIM are emerging as powerful tools in nuclear back-end operations. The potential impact of these technologies includes:

- Improved safety through reduced human exposure to radiation by enabling remote planning and visualisation of decommissioning activities
- Enhanced waste estimation and management, allowing for more accurate predictions of waste volumes and types
- Optimised decommissioning planning and execution, leading to cost savings and shorter project timelines
- Better risk assessment and scenario planning for various dismantling approaches
- Increased transparency and collaboration among stakeholders through shared digital platforms
- Enhanced regulatory compliance and documentation through comprehensive digital records
- Improved integration of robotics and automation in decommissioning processes
- More accurate cost estimation and budget management for decommissioning projects

By analysing the gaps in implementing DT and BIM in the nuclear back-end, based on a literature survey and the opinions of various stakeholders, some of the critical needs and recommendations were highlighted. These include:

- Creating customised DT and BIM solutions through cross-sector technological collaboration
- Establishing international standards and guidelines for DT and BIM in nuclear back-end operations
- Implementing an incremental adoption strategy focusing on high-priority decommissioning tasks
- Conducting cost-benefit analyses and pilot projects to demonstrate the long-term economic benefits, operational efficiencies, and environmental improvements
- Building specialised workforce training programs bridging nuclear engineering and digital skills

- Promoting public understanding and international collaboration for technology adoption

The focus of the analysis was on defining the barriers that impede the adoption of DT and BIM in the nuclear back-end and providing a set of recommendations to the relevant stakeholders. A more detailed list of identified common barriers and potential solutions identified can be found in [41]).

3.3.4 Advanced technology cross topical identified barriers and recommendations

Many of the identified barriers and proposed recommendations were not limited to just one of the studied sub topics.

An overview of the identified barriers and recommendations which were common to at least two of the sub topics is provided in Table 1. Many of the identified cross-cutting barriers preventing the use of advanced technologies were relevant to multiple T-E-C-O-P categories (Technical, Environmental/regulatory, Commercial, Operational, (socio-)Political and so were classed as 'General Aspects' in Table 1.

Table 1 Cross-Topical Findings Related to Advanced Technologies

Category	Challenge	Sub topic Alignment			Recommendation
		Technology assessment	Robotics	DT & BIM	
General Aspects					
Stakeholder communication	Restrictive working relationships between key stakeholders leading to an inability to concisely identify shared objectives and goals.	✓	✓	✓	Establish facilitated platforms to stimulate discussion between various stakeholders (e.g. to raise awareness of impediments and opportunities) and make the results and findings easy-to-access.
Shared awareness of technical solutions	Lack of shared knowledge and awareness of details on existing technologies and their Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	✓	✓	✓	Creation of a centralised, easy-to-access and maintained database on existing technologies (e.g. TRL status, deployment, operational and waste specifications, advantages, limitations, case studies etc.) to create a shared stakeholder awareness
Risk Aversion	The nuclear sector often lags behind other industries in developing and deploying innovative technologies, possibly due to a risk averse culture	✓	✓	✓	Foster cross-industry exchange that also addresses the standards for the implementation of new technologies in the nuclear back-end.

Category	Challenge	Sub topic Alignment			Recommendation
		Technology assessment	Robotics	DT & BIM	
Regulatory requirements	Country-specific regulatory frameworks can hinder adoption of new technologies across borders and often lead to increased costs, e.g. due to requalifications.	✓	✓	✓	Development of universal technical standards to streamline requirements across borders.
Cyber security	Lacking awareness and understanding of (cyber) security aspects, e.g. by developers, the supply chain and end users.	✓	✓	✓	Develop and enforce strong cybersecurity protocols to protect sensitive information. Provision of dedicated training measures.
Technical Aspects					
Standardised development and assessment protocols	Unclear requirements to demonstrate confidence and suitability of system technology in end environment, resulting in re-work and poor technical integration	✓	✓	✓	Standardisation of assessment procedures and awareness of technology development, integration and deployment processes (including lifetime requirements such as maintenance)

Category	Challenge	Sub topic Alignment			Recommendation
		Technology assessment	Robotics	DT & BIM	
International test facilities	Limited access to radioactive materials and testing facilities to demonstrate and validate advanced technologies.	✓	✓		Creation of European sand-box facilities to aid ease of scale-up, versatile deployment and implementation under usual business when developing technologies.
<i>Environmental Aspects</i>					
Varied approach to First-of-a-Kind (FOAK) technology demonstrations	Lack of a consolidated approach for regulating FOAK technologies. Existing regulations not enabling measures to be put in place that are proportional to risk.	✓	✓		Develop and collaborate through 'regulatory sand-boxes' to uncover deeper learning and manage emerging technologies.
Identification of relevant specific guidance and regulatory requirements	Challenge in identifying which guidance and regulatory requirements are most relevant for stakeholders involved in the development of advanced technologies	✓	✓	✓	Development of international standards and guidelines that address the mandatory requirements for implementation of advanced technologies.

		Technology assessment	Robotics	DT & BIM	
Varied certification process	Challenges arising from country-specific legislation and certification mechanisms	✓	✓	✓	Review and when necessary update and standardise regulatory frameworks to accommodate the development and integration of advanced technologies.
Commercial Aspects					
Cost-Benefit-Analysis	Uncertainty about the economic justification for initial investments. Lack of realistic and shared accepted cost projections / models / assumptions, due to uncertainties associated with forecasting lifecycle costs (particularly for many decades into the future), to support effective Cost Benefit Analysis.	✓	✓	✓	Focus on tasks for which the proposed systems offer clear safety and / or economic benefits. Establishing means of adequately comparing the long-term cost consequences of acting and non-acting, and also means of comparing the costs and risks associated with doing work manually against the cost of developing, manufacturing, testing and deploying technological alternatives.

Category	Challenge	Sub topic Alignment			Recommendation
		Technology assessment	Robotics	DT & BIM	
Incentivisation and graded approach	High initial costs (including training) to implementation	✓	✓	✓	Provide modular solutions that allow nuclear facilities to implement specific features incrementally, reducing initial investment costs and complexity. Offer financial incentives or tax breaks to nuclear facilities that adopt advanced technologies.
IP Management	Holders of intellectual property rights can restrict access to information about their products which can lead to higher costs (e.g. for maintenance or disposal).	✓	✓		Improved business culture with respect to embracing new technologies, and the need to establish a clear use case to support challenge statements.
Quality assurance	Lack of solid evidence demonstrating return on investment, and incomplete picture of the benefits.	✓	✓	✓	Clear guidance to enable developers to ensure the impact of new technologies on safety and efficiency is well demonstrated.
Operational Aspects					

Category	Challenge	Sub topic Alignment			Recommendation
		Technology assessment	Robotics	DT & BIM	
Facility transition from Operations to Decommissioning	Challenges along the transition from productive operation to cost-generating decommissioning and dismantling (D&D)	✓		✓	Effective management and transparent communication to support the transfer of viewpoint and personnel from operations to D&D. Involve operational personnel at all stages of design and development to ensure practical insights that enhance safety and usability.
Organisational factors	Organisational aspects impeding innovations, including staff requirements, necessary initial investments and integration into existing systems and processes.	✓	✓	✓	Provision of suitable and standardised training measures supported by digital tools, if needed. Allocation of sufficient budgets to build competencies, including upskilling.
<i>Socio-Political Aspects</i>					
Public opinion	Lack of public acceptance, e. g. due to concerns regarding safety and environmental impacts.		✓	✓	Emphasise the benefits for society and outline potential future applications to gain the support, prioritise transparency, community engagement and open dialogue.
Funding	Lack of adequate / consistent funding and financial support for the development of new technologies.	✓	✓		Provision of funding to advance promising low-TRL (TRL 1 to TRL 6) technologies, thereby enabling the development and testing needed for future deployment.

Category	Challenge	Sub topic Alignment			Recommendation	
		Technology assessment	Robotics	DT & BIM		
Loss of workforce	Loss of institutional knowledge and challenging recruitment. Workforce and resource challenges can lead to the loss of experienced personnel and poor knowledge transfer.	✓	✓		Provide adequate budgets to implement a structured knowledge management system to ensure that institutional knowledge is spread among different people and captured with suitable means. Use of mentors to assist new professionals.	

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4 Conclusions and Recommendations towards harmonisation

Based on the deeper analysis with the stakeholder community, recommendations towards harmonisation are listed for the three themes.

These conclusions and recommendations are to be complemented with the conclusions from report *D6.1 Regulatory framework and criteria report* [44], which consolidates insights from expert consultations, stakeholder input and regulatory analysis to identify recurring challenges and propose areas for improvement focused on regulatory aspects only.

4.1 Cross border activities

The cross-border treatment of nuclear waste in European member states is a multifaceted challenge that requires careful coordination and collaboration. Addressing regulatory disparities, mitigating transportation risks, managing public perception, and resolving questions of equity are essential steps toward effective cross-border waste management. By fostering trust, enhancing infrastructure, and promoting transparency, the EU can strengthen its collective approach to nuclear waste treatment while ensuring safety and sustainability for future generations.

Cross border radioactive waste management activities can result in significant benefits including:

- Reducing the cost of treatment.
- Encouragement of smaller waste inventories to be treated.
- Utilising the best available technology.
- Benefiting from variances in national regulatory policy/priorities.

More generally, cross border treatment can support the circular economy principles for certain wastes/assets but can also contribute to a more sustainable and resource-efficient approach to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management.

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A series of recommendations are summarized which will help to continue the alignment to the waste hierarchy for MS.

From a **Regulatory** perspective, the recommendations are:

- Ensure that each MS's legislation allows the radioactive waste export for processing or the import of other countries' radioactive waste for processing and conditioning, mirrored with legislation for retrieval of secondary waste after treatment.
- Resolution of the regulatory conflicts at a National and European level regarding waste which is both radioactive and hazardous.
- Some MS are not part of OECD, so cannot benefit from utilising cross-border treatment options, this must be resolved to promote waste management best practice.

From a **Technical** perspective, the recommendations are:

- Development of a European platform to identify all European infrastructure available for use by MS. Some MS do not have sufficient infrastructure to handle waste, leading to delays or inaction.
- Define European wide Best Available Technology (BAT) approach for material and waste characterisation and treatment, based on established practices and new approaches. European wide agreed approaches may incentivise cross border facilities and services.
- Ensure that waste management techniques are sufficiently demonstrated for national regulators or waste owners – this must cover simple and complex waste forms and ensure that there is a suitable forum for sharing information across MS for MS stakeholders to engage with and develop the necessary requirements to allow for internal treatment, or utilising cross border facilities
- Ensure that all MS's agree on the definition of problematic waste and that it is included within the individual MS legislation.
- Develop Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC) for all types of waste to allow for final disposal.
- For the radioactive hazardous waste groups that were investigated (mercury, asbestos and lead), the capability to treat and dispose of these wastes was not

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uniformly available across responding countries, so the development and utilisation of cross-border solutions could provide a means of overcoming current barriers to the management of these wastes.

- There appears to be a strong case for enhanced recycling / reuse of radiologically contaminated lead wastes, noting that there is expected to be future demand for this material, e.g. as a coolant in some SMR/AMR designs.

By adopting these recommendations and fostering a collaborative approach among stakeholders, the nuclear industry can improve the way it manages its radioactive waste through the utilisation of cross border facilities.

4.2 Circular Economy

Integrating circular economy principles into nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management can result in significant benefits:

- reducing consumption of raw materials,
- decreasing the amount of radioactive and non-radioactive wastes (by reusing and recycling as much as possible),
- optimising the use of available resources by repurposing of facilities and/or sites,
- lowering cost and environmental impacts,
- decommissioning process innovation.

Applying circular economy approaches can contribute to a more sustainable and resource-efficient approach to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste and materials management.

Some already well implemented practices exist, but there are still several significant challenges to integrate circular economy principles in current and future decommissioning and waste management projects.

From a technical point of view, one of the main challenges is the limited capacity of existing technologies to decontaminate and detect slightly contaminated radioactive materials, which restricts their recyclability and reuse. Regarding the regulatory framework, differences in national regulations create ambiguity in the application of clearance levels, and treatment of the different material streams, leading to

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inconsistencies that may impact public acceptance and trust in radioactive materials management practices. In addition, public perception about recycling of radioactive materials remains a significant barrier. To address these challenges, it is *essential to implement innovative solutions, to promote and support ongoing research and development, and to develop a robust evaluation framework that includes clearly defined and measurable criteria to assess the overall benefits of various strategies.*

From a **regulatory** perspective: *a harmonization of radioactive materials clearance practices at the European level is needed, which could be achieved through the establishment of a European working group to develop common guidelines. Recycling and reuse should, in one way or another, be considered in decommissioning plans, designs and permitting procedures, during both the preparatory and implementation phases.*

From a **technical** point of view: the key point is to be able to meet the radiological thresholds that demonstrate that the materials are below the clearance levels. *Research and development efforts should focus on improving decontamination technologies, optimizing separation processes to maximize the reuse of materials and improving techniques to enable easier and faster measurement of (volumetric) activity.*

From a **social** perspective: *promoting transparency and stakeholders' engagement practices is crucial for improving acceptance of radioactive material recycling. The creation of a shared database documenting case studies could strengthen trust among stakeholders.*

Some Suggestions have been identified for approaching harmonization at European level (Figure 2):

1. **Establish a European task force or working group.** Create a dedicated task force under an existing European body such as the *European Atomic Energy Community (EURATOM)* or the *European Commission* to focus on harmonizing regulations for the conditional and unconditional release of materials (review radiation protection reports, e.g. RP89, 122, etc.). This task force could include representatives from regulatory bodies, the nuclear industry, and research institutions across member states to ensure broad input and expertise.

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2. **Develop European technical guidelines based on best practices.** Introduce a set of European-wide guidelines or a "Code of Practice" that promotes waste hierarchy and outlines standardized procedures for the release, recycling and reuse of materials. These guidelines should be based on scientific research, practical case studies, and international standards (e.g., IAEA guidelines) to ensure consistency and transparency across countries.
3. **Implement a centralized database for material release, recycling and reuse cases.** Create a shared European database documenting case studies of conditional and unconditional release, recycling and reuse. This database would provide transparency, allow stakeholders to learn from successful and unsuccessful cases, and serve as a reference for both authorities and industry to better interpret regulations in complex scenarios.
4. **Pilot cross-border harmonization projects.** Conduct pilot projects involving multiple European countries to test and refine harmonized release protocols. For example, joint initiatives could focus on specific material types, such as concrete or metal, allowing for a comparison of results and regulatory processes across borders.
5. **Foster research collaboration and innovation.** Encourage collaborative research initiatives across European universities and research centres focusing on innovative decontamination and material characterization technologies. Funding programs such as *Horizon Europe* could support projects aimed at improving processes for the conditional release of materials, making them safer and more efficient.
6. **Promote public and stakeholder engagement.** Increase transparency and public understanding to build trust in the reuse of decommissioned materials. Organize workshops and public fora involving stakeholders such as environmental organizations, local communities, and industry representatives to ensure their concerns are addressed early in the process.
7. **Standardized training and certification programs.** Develop standardized training programs for professionals involved in material handling, decontamination, and regulatory enforcement. A Europe-wide certification system would ensure consistency in the understanding and application of harmonized regulations and circular economy approaches.
8. **Legislative roadmap with phased implementation.** Create a phased roadmap for regulatory harmonization, starting with simpler materials (e.g., metals, plastics) and progressing to more complex cases (e.g., mixed waste). This gradual approach would allow time for testing, refinement, and adjustment based on feedback and real-world application.

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By adopting these recommendations and fostering a collaborative approach among stakeholders, the nuclear industry can effectively transition to a more sustainable and resource-efficient model, enhancing both operational practices and public acceptance of nuclear decommissioning processes.

Figure 2: Graphical representation of the suggested harmonisation approaches related to circular economy

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4.3 Advanced technologies

Advanced technologies have the potential to improve the safety and security of all nuclear related activities. Therefore, it is in the interest of the nuclear sector and the public that any required new technologies become implemented in a timely fashion – always under the strict requirement that there are no compromises regarding safety and security. It should be noted that the use of such technologies is not necessarily restricted to current nuclear back-end activities. It is likely that these technologies - in combination with the gained experience and knowledge during the R&D process – can also provide added value to other areas of investment in future nuclear developments including new-builds – such as Advanced Nuclear Technologies (e.g. High Temperature Gas-cooled Reactors (HTGRs)), Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), Gen 3+4 and fusion reactors – and also other highly regulated industries.

Many of the barriers related to the implementation of advanced technologies are related to a lack-of-information and difficult-to-find or missing information (including guidance and norms) for the key stakeholders, including decision makers and business case developers. Keeping in mind that – unlike the nuclear front end – the majority of nuclear back-end activities (such as decommissioning) usually do not lead to additional revenues (for the facility owner), the perception of cost benefits and investment, is different. Hence, having a strong business case that clearly sets out the benefits of risk reduction and/or cost savings for implementation of advanced technologies in the nuclear back-end is therefore essential.

It is obvious that advanced technologies will have certain implications for the workforce, e.g. human factors considerations, qualification requirements and the required number of workers needed for specific tasks. Therefore, an essential requirement for a successful and safe application of new technologies is the acceptance by those who will have to work with them.

In general, it can be stated, that the perception of barriers and the relevance of recommendations usually depends on the different stakeholder perspectives. Hence, communication and alignment of purpose and understanding between different

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stakeholders is a key element to gain a better understanding of different needs and problems.

Activities that should promote greater alignment of approaches at a European level to support implementation of advanced technologies have been identified and can be grouped and categorised as follows:

1. **Establish European working group(s) for common challenges.**
Establishment of European platforms to promote and facilitate discussions between different stakeholders and to foster cross-industry exchange and collaboration. The working groups created would focus on high impact challenges for which the proposed advanced technologies offer clear safety and / or economic benefits against shared objectives and goals.
2. **Develop common guidelines and identification of good practices.**
Development of universal standards, protocols and guidelines to support standardised assessment and implementation of advanced technologies across borders (e.g. cyber assessments). There is a cross-topical need for guidance and technical norms that will provide an added value for both end-users and regulators / supervisory authorities.
3. **Creation and maintenance of a centralised knowledge database.**
Implementation of a centralised and easy-to-access database of existing technologies and case studies to share learning and experience. Varied stakeholder communication will be vastly improved with a shared point of referenceable information.
4. **Cross-border harmonisation of test facilities.**
Creation of European sand-box⁵ approaches and facilities to support testing with respect to development and regulation of new technologies. Skills, costs and risks could then be shared and common ways of working agreed and then adopted.
5. **Standardised training and certification programmes.** Implementation of universally recognised training courses and certification supported by digital tools. This would enable developers to ensure the impact of new technologies on safety and efficiency is well demonstrated and a limited work force could be shared between facilities.

⁵ Sand-boxes generally refer to tools allowing businesses to test and experiment with new and innovative products, services or businesses under supervision of a regulator for a limited period of time.

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6. **Establish a shared methodology for business case analysis.** Development of a standardised methodology for conducting cost-benefit analysis with shared industry assumptions. There is a requirement to adequately compare the long-term cost consequences of acting and non-acting in decommissioning strategy planning, in addition to the costs and risks associated with doing work manually, against the cost of developing, manufacturing, testing and deploying technological alternatives. This would also help long term work force planning, knowledge management and common life cycle assessments.

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5 Business cases

After identifying obstacles and issues that may hamper more aligned methodologies and approaches and formulating recommendations as to how to overcome them, the HARPERS project also developed Business Cases in which Cases for Change are proposed that show the potential benefit of the change compared to the base case.

The aim is to provide stakeholders/decision makers evidence related to the “case for change” to support decision making towards (future) Strategic Research Agenda’s.

Within the business cases we describe what is suboptimal about the present situation and if we do things different, what might be the benefit. The benefits/impacts are structured along the T-E-C-O-P categories (Technological, Environmental/regulatory, Commercial/economic, Operational and socio-Political).

The information feeding these business cases stems from the deeper analysis of a selection of key topics, by engaging a wide variety of stakeholders, for which the outcome is described in previous chapters.

5.1 Business case model used

The model used for the HARPERS business cases is the Five Case Model (45), where each business case is made up of 5 separate parts or cases (Figure 3). Each case focuses on a “specific aspect” of the overall business case. The importance of, and detail required in each case, is dependent upon the maturity of the business case.

The business cases developed under HARPERS are *initial Business cases*, where the focus is primarily on the *Strategic Case* with some consideration to the *Economic Case*.

The Strategic Case describes the strategic requirements and outlines the case for change while the Economic Case investigates the options to achieve the desired outcomes identified in the strategic case and examines the value that different options deliver.

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Figure 3: the 5 case business model used for the HARPERS business cases, with emphasis on the initial business case phase.

For each of the themes (Cross border, Circular economy, Advanced Technologies) investigated in the HARPERS project, several “cases for change” have been provided in the business cases.

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5.2 Cross border – Business case

Nuclear installations are designed, commissioned and in operation for many years. At end of life, the facility has to be decommissioned. Throughout the operational life, waste will be generated and components replaced. At end of life, all installations have to be taken care of and the facility must be decommissioned.

The materials and waste streams can be managed locally on the site. These will be packed for disposal in a final repository, or sent for treatment at an external domestic treatment facility, or a facility across borders prior to disposal of the waste in the country of origin.

Shipment of radioactive waste to another country for final disposal is not an accepted practice within Europe. For this reason, this report is mainly focused on cross border waste treatment.

An external facility can be either a shared facility or a facility owned and operated by a company providing services on commercial basis.

This Business Case (BC) outlines the current situation, identified hurdles, provides analysis, proposes cases for change and recommendations related to cross border radioactive waste management treatment within Europe. The document is based on the outcome of intensive stakeholder engagement and discussions in the EC HARPERS related to the theme “Cross Border” (WP3).

Five proposals for changes have been defined in the Case for Change section related to:

- Harmonisation/Standardisation of Radioactive and Hazardous Waste Definitions. (Case for Change 1)
- Europe to adopt a European wide and well-defined Best Available Technology (BAT) approach for waste characterisation and treatment based on established practices and new approaches. (Case for Change 2)
- Reducing the stocks of legacy/historical radioactive waste in Europe by co-founded centralized treatment facilities. (Case for Change 3)
- Utilisation of cross-border treatment options for radiologically-contaminated hazardous wastes. (Case for Change 4)

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- Generate a set of standard Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC), standardised packages etc. for new disposal facilities in Europe. (Case for Change 5)

5.2.1 Problem statement

Current situation

There are currently examples of cross-border radioactive waste management activities that work well. One example is the shipments of metals and organic wastes to Sweden for treatment in isolated campaigns and the later return of residues for disposal in the country of origin.

At the same time, organisations face difficulties either to ship contaminated metals and radioactive waste abroad for treatment, or to get acceptance for temporary import for treatment.

Transportation is to a large extent a well working established practice thanks to the European transport regulations ADR (transport on road), RID (transport on rail) and IMDG (transport on water). However, the stakeholder views on this established practice may differ and certain additional requirements implemented in the national legislation.

There are to date, and as known, no fully shared facilities, i.e. facilities with shared ownership, for border crossing radioactive waste services. However, there are some companies which, with their own facilities, are providing cross border services, on commercial basis, related to contaminated materials and radioactive waste. Such facilities, within the European Union, are at date located in France, Germany, Slovakia and Sweden. The services are currently limited to those applicable to metals and organic wastes.

In this document, the term 'shared facilities' applied to those owned and operated by one organisation that provided services across borders.

Identified hurdles and problems:

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1. Suitable facilities, methods, skills and tools are not available within the country.
2. Shortage of domestic rules and regulations related to waste conditioning, accepted primary containers, package qualification, etc.
3. Inventories that are too small to establish domestic treatment facilities.
4. Legal, practical and commercial hurdles for the implementation of shared facilities.
5. Different legislative/regulatory rules and views on what is material and what is waste.
6. Different interpretations, add on requirements or limitations of the EURATOM/2013/59 directive (the European Basic Safety Standards) and other directives, standards or international recommendations.
7. Criteria related to clearance of materials and ownership impacting the clearance and release of materials in another country.
8. Different rules for the management of wastes which are both hazardous (due to the non-radiological properties) and radioactive.
9. Several stakeholders are involved in the process related to cross border services, not at least the relevant regulatory bodies (mandatory). This applies to the country of origin, transit countries (to the extent applicable) and the country of treatment.

Item 1 and 3 relates to domestic shortcomings.

Item 4 to 9 relates to hurdles preventing to cross border activities.

5.2.2 Analysis

In this section we describe and summarise the identified pros and cons when comparing cross border treatment activities with the base line. The base line is assumed to be waste treatment at the site where the redundant materials and the waste arises taking benefit of local resources, facilities and the domestic supply chain. No domestic external treatment facility is foreseen in the baseline.

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5.2.2.1 Technical aspects

Physical

The physical properties should not be underestimated. In many cases, the physical properties of objects exclude either the local management or the shipment to a specialized facility. The assessments of physical properties are typically related to size and weight, but the detailed design of objects can be of great importance as well, not at least if the material is aimed for clearance and recycling.

The *size of objects* to be managed might be both a driver and a hurdle for cross border management of contaminated materials.

Large objects are typically hard to manage at the location of the installation. At the same time, shipment of large objects can be complicated, not least if the objects are to be transported on road or rail, and have dimensions which are larger than for what the road and rail systems have been designed for. Level crossings etc. might make transports complex, or even not at all possible. For transports on waterways, the object dimensions are typically not a problem. The size of the objects might also be a complexing factor at a specialised treatment facility in another country and should be addressed in the initial planning phase.

Somewhat similar to the discussion about the size of objects, *the weight* might be both a driver and a hurdle for cross border management of contaminated materials.

Heavy objects to be managed and disassembled/segmented locally will typically require cranes with significant capacity or other lifting equipment at the location of disassembly. Also, the allowed loads on floors etc. In the case of cross border shipment, the allowed weights, especially for road transport could be significant hurdle to manage. The weight is typically not a problem for transport on waterways and on rail. For transport on waterways, very heavy objects (several hundred tonnes per component), special crane arrangements might be required unless roll-on/roll-off is possible for the actual vessel.

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The weight might be challenging also for the specialized treatment facility. As for the size, the weight limitations should be addressed in the early planning phase.

The *detailed design of objects* to be managed has mainly an impact on the disassembly, segmentation and further treatment. The objective of the management may have a large impact on the assessment whether to manage the object locally or at a specialized facility. Special attention should be given to assembled objects, composed of different materials and contaminated on many surfaces.

Radiological

The radiological aspects are typically the most discussed technical parameters.

Depending on the specific properties for the object and the objective with the management of the components, the weighing of the different radiological properties may differ.

In a handling and transportation perspective, the external dose rate and the potential non-fixed contamination on the external surfaces may be the key properties.

In a treatment perspective, the dose rates on the exposed internal surfaces, the amount of non-fixed contamination and location of the contamination might be the critical parameters.

In a clearance perspective, the nuclide composition and the conditions for efficient decontamination might be the key parameters.

For the planning of the residual waste management, the total inventory and the quality of the nuclide vector might be the most important parameters, not at least if the treatment process will provide a significant transfer of the radioactivity to the residual waste (treatment of surface contaminated metals) or a substantial mass reduction (thermal treatment of organic waste).

The radiological parameters which most affect whether an object should be managed locally or in a specialized facility typically relates to;

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- the objective with the treatment (disassembly/segmentation aiming for clearance and recycling or for disposal as radioactive waste)
- nuclide inventory
- accessibility for decontamination
- quality of nuclide vector.

Related to the nuclide inventory; the more alpha emitters, caesium and strontium, the more advantageous it is to perform thermal treatment of especially metals, i.e. metal melting. This since the mentioned nuclides separates from the metal and get concentrated in the slag and filter dust.

It must also be noted that metals treated by a process involving melting is much more forgiving when it comes to the possibilities to reach the criteria for clearance.

Chemical

The chemical properties may affect the possibilities to treat, clear/recycle and/or dispose a material.

Examples include;

- galvanised steel can have a significant impact on both treatment and final disposal (hydrogen generation in geological disposal)
- aluminium (hydrogen generation in geological disposal can be a major concern)
- combination of different materials can have an impact on treatment, clearance and recycling and final disposal
- organics can have an impact on clearance and final disposal

Hazardous elements

Hazardous materials, for example lead, as well as materials containing or contaminated with hazardous elements may affect the possibilities to handle, treat, recycle and/or dispose a material.

The preference is to treat/qualify such materials for general or specific clearance, either for recycling or reuse (primarily lead), or for further handling as conventional hazardous waste.

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Table 2. Key Technical pros and cons with cross border services compared to baseline.

	Pros	Cons
Physical	Reduced need for investments in facilities and capabilities for treatment of special items.	Transport of objects for treatment and return of residues.
Radiological	Better possibilities to keep doses low in a specialized and dedicated facility. Increased possibilities to qualify a material for clearance and recycling, thanks to more efficient decontamination and melting.	Transboundary transports of radioactive materials and waste might be a hurdle in some countries
Chemical	Possibility to decontaminate and recycle also certain less common, but in some aspects problematic materials (such as aluminium, galvanised steel, copper, etc.) and hazardous materials (lead etc.)	Minimum quantities for external treatment from one licensee must be reached (isolated campaigns).
Hazardous elements	Cross border facilities can, considering the wider market, be designed for treatment of objects containing hazardous elements.	Hazardous elements might be complicated for external treatment unless the dedicated facility is designed and licensed for treatment of such elements.

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5.2.2.2 Environmental and regulatory aspects

Environmental aspects

The key environmental aspects are nowadays related to the waste hierarchy and sustainability. In several European countries, the waste hierarchy should be applied. It means in practice that materials are to be reused or recycled inside or outside the nuclear industry. Any upfront characterisation and the treatment activities should aim for reuse and recycling to the extent technically possible and reasonable in cost. This means in practice that most materials can be managed in an efficient way locally, but that some materials may of technical and/or commercial reasons be subject to treatment in specialized facilities in another country, if the service is not available on the domestic market.

In a short-term perspective, it might be cheaper to perform specific clearance or other type of qualification of materials for disposal in dedicated landfills even though the material can be subject to recycling. This is not in line with the sustainability principles and should not be allowed, unless a recycling option is considered unreasonable in a full life cycle analysis.

Table 3. Key Environmental pros and cons with cross border services compared to baseline.

	Pros	Cons
Sustainable material management	Higher percentage clearance and recycling.	Transboundary shipments, potentially long, causing emissions.
Saving of repository volume	Less need for nuclear licensed disposal volumes.	All already built disposal capacity might not be needed. Higher disposal cost per cubic meter of waste if the repository will not be fully utilized.

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Regulatory aspects

The regulatory aspects, including permits and, licenses play an important role for any practice or project. The introduction and implementation of new governing principles, like the waste hierarchy, might put a massive burden on the regulators as well as the industry both in terms of workload and to achieve a reasonable schedule.

Table 4. Key Regulatory pros and cons with cross border services compared to baseline.

	Pros	Cons
Regulatory framework for project	Robust and proven regulatory framework for treatment in country of treatment.	Certain considerations of the regulatory framework in country of origin and in country of treatment.
Alignment with waste hierarchy	Easier to fulfil the governmental requirements on application of sustainability principles and the waste hierarchy.	Regulatory concerns regarding international shipments of radioactive materials and waste.
Low risks/ risk reduction	Proven and well-defined solutions.	Involvement of multiple regulatory frameworks and regulatory bodies.
Supervision and cooperation beyond borders	International cooperation, possibility to take benefit of leading technologies and proven solutions.	Need for management of differences between regulatory systems.

5.2.2.3 Commercial aspects

The commercial aspects related to material and waste management can be assessed from many different perspectives, in general or specifically related to whether to apply cross border management services.

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The main alternatives for the material and waste owners are typically to make assessments of the following alternatives;

1. Integration of material and waste management/treatment in the decommissioning organization at the facility to be decommissioned. Typically, areas within the facility are re-arranged to be a local waste management centre.
2. Construction of a new local waste treatment facility next to the facility to be decommissioned.
3. A fleet approach where centralized or spread-out resources are arranged for management and treatment of the redundant materials and the wastes generated.
4. Outsourcing of material and waste management and treatment to a specialized organisation. The specialized facility might be located within the country or abroad. Be a shared facility or a facility operated by one organisation providing services on commercial basis.

There are good examples of all four alternatives above. In most cases, it is during a decommissioning project where, for strategic and practical reasons, a combination of two or three of the alternatives are preferred.

For the definition of the most suitable and cost efficient alternative or combination of alternatives to be applied on a specific program or project, a multi criteria analysis should be performed. The assessment should at least include the following parameters;

- Total cost analysis (develop, operate and decommission)
- Economy of scale versus a local dedicated solution
- Financial risk. In the case the alternatives provide significant amounts of residual waste, the financial risk related to uncertainties about future disposal of radioactive waste.

Specific to the question about shared facilities or facilities provided on a commercial basis, there are a number of pros and cons.

With a shared facility opportunities, investments, responsibilities, risks and liabilities are to be shared:

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- A specific organisation has to be the owner and licensee of any nuclear licensed facility. This will limit or at least complicate the possibility for a full distribution of responsibilities.
- A nuclear licensed processing facility is a commitment over several decades from project initiation to completed decommissioning. The need for external material and waste management capacity varies over the operational lifetime for a facility from small yearly volumes (most years) to significant peaks during large maintenance and upgrade projects, normally once a decade or even more seldom. During decommissioning there will be some peaks spread out over a few years before it is over.
- A shared facility where the owners book certain capacity during a specific period of time, is very sensitive to delays in the maintenance and decommissioning projects.

Table 5. Key Commercial pros and cons with cross border services compared to baseline.

	Pros	Cons
Total operational cost	Higher utilization, specialized workforce in dedicated facility should keep operational treatment costs down.	Higher operational cost to cover for investments done, future decommissioning and contractor profit. Additional costs related to transport.
Investments, including end of life costs	Investments as well as decommissioning funding are by others.	Investments as well as decommissioning funding might be a heavy burden, unless existing facilities and investments can be used.
Economy of scale	Good potential to take benefit of economy of scales.	For unique objects, no benefit of economy of scale. Significant risk for low utilization of workforce and facility over time.

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Financial risk	In the case the treatment significantly will reduce the amount of residual waste for disposal compared to the local solution, the financial risk will reduce. The latter conditioned to that the new waste form can be qualified for disposal.	
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5.2.2.4 Operational aspects

Key operational aspects, in addition to what has been mentioned in the previous section (commercial aspects), are among others to secure that the facility and the associated tools are fit and authorised for the intended task, that properly trained and qualified resources are available and that the material can be transported to and accommodated at the place of treatment.

Table 6. Key Operational pros and cons with cross border services compared to baseline.

	Pros	Cons
Facility and tools fit and authorised for task	Responsibility with the external dedicated shared facility.	Dependence on external parties.
Proper resources	Resources will be available, but not locally and governed by commercial agreements	Dependence on external stakeholders
Local competence	Allow object owner focus on being the intelligent customer.	Cross border shipment for treatment will build less local competence
External shipment	Evacuation from site – transfer of task to external parties	Need to establish shipment routes, transportation knowledge.

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5.2.2.5 Political and socio-political aspects

In most countries, any nuclear activity known to public may get significant attention. Shortage of solutions to manage radioactive waste, increase in stock of radioactive waste, delays in decommissioning programs and cost overruns are typically highly political. Also, transport of radioactive waste and release of material and waste from nuclear practices might cause public concerns and by then potentially political attention.

There are also socio-political aspects related to a potential implementation of cross border services. It may span from concerns about local jobs to expectations on shortening of decommissioning schedule to open for new businesses, and by then new job opportunities taking benefit of the facility or the site.

Table 7. Key Political and socio-political pros and cons with cross border services compared to baseline.

	Pros	Cons
Political	Reduction of decommissioning schedule by contracting out work to external parties.	Transport of radioactive materials on public roads, rail and waterways.
Sociopolitical	Earlier release of site for new businesses or other use.	Loss of local jobs.

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5.2.3 Cases for change

Based on the stakeholder interactions, five cases for change have been defined.

5.2.3.1 Case for Change 1: Harmonisation/Standardisation of Radioactive and Hazardous Waste Definitions.

Background:

- In some MS, metal aimed for recycling must not be classified as waste. In other MS, it must be classified as nuclear or radioactive waste up to completion of clearance.
- MS has a variety of terms for radioactive waste, for example: VLLW, LLW etc. as well as short lived, long lived. Not all member states use the same definitions, or that there are significant differences in definitions, which causes hurdles and is a source of misunderstandings for cross border activities. There is a similar situation for hazardous waste.

Outcomes:

- Change or focus from most materials inside a nuclear installation being waste, to demonstrating them as resources for reuse and recycling. Aligns with the waste hierarchy and the strive towards a circular economy as well as an incentive for the opening of cross border activities.
- A uniformed approach and understanding of definitions for radioactive and hazardous wastes (and materials), could then lead to an approach for aligned waste treatment legislation.
- Reduced risk for Stakeholder confusion and loss of trust if the same terminology/meaning is used across borders.
- Increased Stakeholder engagement and adoption of treatment best practices.
- Simplifies cross border treatment of wastes, when beneficial.
- Additional highly utilised treatment facilities within Europe, based on a wider waste market. Additional treatment facilities in combination with standardised definitions would reduce the legacy waste and demonstrate that nuclear is sustainable.
- Underpin the development of new technologies for treating waste across the member states and overseas.

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5.2.3.2 Case for Change 2: Europe to adopt a European wide and well-defined Best Available Technology (BAT) approach for waste characterisation and treatment based on established practices and new approaches.

Background:

- Identification of the required characterisation information and defined good practice, especially focusing on legacy/historical wastes.
- Techniques and Technologies for treatment can be categorised to align with the Waste Framework Directive and its targets.
- An End Producer Responsibility (EPR) Scheme can be established for Nuclear Waste in general or for specific nuclear waste forms.
- Experience to date demonstrates that Regulator engagement throughout the characterisation, treatment and clearance or disposal is crucial and an adopted EU BAT agreement would support engagement and adoption.
- Technology Readiness Level (TRL) processes and technologies with potential for enhancement can be identified and detailed European development paths can be established to move through the TRL process and give confidence to the Stakeholders.
- This would also improve the knowledge and experience of Stakeholders, which will support the implementation of the waste hierarchy. Safe and efficient recycling/reuse as well as well-defined waste forms for safe disposal.

Outcomes:

- Local and EU Stakeholder confidence gained through learning and understanding of applicable technologies and processes. This will likely lead to an improved management of wastes, applying specific technologies when beneficial.
- Could be an important parameter into common WACs (Case for Change 4)
- Increased support and development of the Waste Framework Directive.
- Adoption and enhancement of waste treatment technologies and processes within member states or across borders.
- Development of new technologies for treating waste across the member states for export outside of the EU.

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5.2.3.3 Case for Change 3: Reducing the stocks of legacy/historical radioactive waste in Europe by co-founded centralized treatment facilities.

Background:

- Europe has waste that is stored because the mandatory waste characteristics are not available and/or waste routes are neither defined nor existing for several reasons.
- The required waste treatment in member states is either not available or not capable due to the high cost of establishing and licensing a treatment facility or specific process.
- A standardised treatment approach accepted cross borders for certain waste forms (e.g. resins) providing a volume reduction would prove economically and environmentally beneficial for MS, as opposed to the base line approach causing a significant volume increase by encapsulating it in cement.
- Cost of treatment is prohibitive – Stakeholders can allow treatment of waste forms in some MS, but the cost of treatment, the volume of waste, the shortage of mandatory characterisation information or the risk profile of the waste means it's not set as a priority for treatment at this stage.

Outcomes:

- Viable and sufficient return on investment for centralised treatment facilities which are either Government or Private Sector owned/operated. A further promotion of cross border waste transport will open the market for investment decisions in waste treatment due to a significantly increased volume of waste available for treatment.
- Cost savings will be recognised through the reduction in “hotel costs” for the continued storage of wastes in their current form.
- Member state/waste owners would then support the waste hierarchy through the use of centralised facilities.
- A reduction of legacy/historical radioactive waste would simplify the licensing of new nuclear installations.

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5.2.3.4 Case for Change 4: Utilisation of cross-border treatment options for radiologically-contaminated hazardous wastes.

Background

- Mercury, asbestos and lead (Pb) have been investigated within the project.
- The capability to treat and dispose of radiologically-contaminated hazardous wastes seems not uniformly available across countries, so the development and utilisation of cross-border solutions may provide a means of overcoming current barriers to the management of these wastes.
- This is particularly relevant where countries have small inventories, for which it could be disproportionately costly to develop dedicated national treatment facilities.
- Cross-border solutions for the treatment and recycling / reuse of lead are an existing and proven practice, provided that the residues from such treatment are returned to the country of origin. Metal which has been qualified for clearance may be shipped for recycling by the service provider.

Outcomes:

- There appears to be a strong case for enhanced recycling / reuse of radiologically-contaminated lead, consistent with widespread drivers for enhanced application of the waste hierarchy.
- The recovered lead can be recycled within or outside the nuclear industry. There is expected to be future demand for this material, e.g. as a coolant in some SMR/AMR designs.
- Recycling radiological lead is current practice in a small number of countries, but disposal routes are more commonly reported. Therefore, it is recommended to examine the feasibility of applying existing decontamination capabilities more widely (and/or expanding these capabilities).
- Enhanced application of the waste hierarchy with regard to lead has strong financial drivers, in terms of its recovery as a future resource and diversion away from repositories, and also strong environmental drivers, since the disposal of large quantities of lead can pose a challenge to compliance with the EC Groundwater Daughter Directive (GWDD).
- There is also a strong case for change with regard to the safe, long-term management of radiologically-contaminated mercury. Here, although many countries report inventories, there is no established treatment or recycling pathway for mercury wastes arising within the nuclear industry.
- Within the conventional industry there is a small recycling market which might be utilised for mercury from the nuclear industry if it could be subject to clearance and if acceptance criteria for available infrastructures could be met. Otherwise, a

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concerted effort will be needed to establish a dedicated waste management solution specifically for radiological mercury.

- Here, there are strong drivers for a collaborative effort to develop a shared solution:
 - From a financial / technological perspective, the technology readiness levels of potential treatment routes such as sulphidisation are currently quite low. Moreover, whilst many countries hold stocks of radiologically-contaminated mercury, in all cases these are rather small, such that national programmes may prefer to prioritise developing management solutions for other, larger, waste streams.
 - There are also strong safety and environmental drivers for effective management of mercury, noting the chemotoxic as well as radiotoxic hazard it poses and, as for lead, the challenge it could pose to compliance with the GWDD.
 - Benefits of a shared solution include the avoidance of duplication of effort by each participating country; possible cost reduction arising from the economy of scale; and better management of uncertainty arising from the absence of a current disposal route, which is the situation faced by many countries.
 - Even though there has been a ban since decades on using asbestos in new products, member states would benefit of cross border cooperation related to qualification of the waste for disposal.
 - Initiatives related to the thermal treatment of asbestos (destruction of the hazard) as well as recycling of the non-hazardous residuals from such treatment into e.g., construction materials may be more efficiently developed utilising cross-border cooperation.

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5.2.3.5 Case for Change 5: Generate a set of standard Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC), standardised packages etc. for new disposal facilities in Europe.

Background

- A set standardised LLW WAC and standardised waste packages would lead to more waste being treated and residues disposed of at an earlier date across Europe.
- Compliance with the WAC is acceptable to stakeholders as demonstrated through the questionnaire results, but also by the examples of metal treatment. A standardised WAC can give sufficient confidence to the regulator for licensing and disposal at the appropriate facility/repository.
- Even though primarily intended for new disposal facilities, the standardised WACs and standardised waste packages would likely be beneficial also for existing disposal facilities.

Outcomes:

- Aligned waste treatment legislation for specific LLW waste forms,
- Set of standard primary containers and waste packages (container with waste).
- Increased Stakeholder engagement and adoption of treatment best practices.
- This would promote, support and speed up cross border treatment of wastes not at least for MS with smaller volumes of waste. No need for iteration to find a country specific waste package concept for residues.
- Increased volume of waste identified for treatment, leading to either a stabilisation, a volume reduction and/or a reuse (circular economy) of materials.
- Dedicated efficient and well utilised treatment facilities would therefore lead to lower costs, reduce the amount of legacy/historical waste and by then improve the reputation of the nuclear industry.
- Complete and efficient LLW solutions will reduce the amount of waste directly disposed using historical approaches.
- Individual MS can then amend local laws and rules, which will be underpinned by EC centralised regulation (such as an amendment to the Waste Framework Directive) to allow for transportation of waste to another country for treatment.

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5.2.4 Recommendations

- Harmonisation/alignment of definitions related to what is a contaminated material (a potential asset) and what is a radioactive waste, as outlined in Case for Change 1 and with strong links to sustainability and circular economy (WP4).
- Strive towards harmonisation/alignment of common definitions for radioactive waste, hazardous waste and not at least for hazardous waste contaminated with radionuclides to underpin cross border facilities and services, as outlined in Case for Change 1.
- Define European wide and well-defined Best Available Technology (BAT) approaches for material and waste characterisation and treatment, based on established practices and new approaches as outlined in Case for Change 2. European wide agreed approaches may incentivise cross border facilities and services.
- Reduce the stocks of legacy/historical radioactive waste in Europe by co-founded shared treatment facilities across borders as outlined in Case for Change 3.
- Identification and utilisation of cross-border treatment and knowledge sharing options for radiologically-contaminated hazardous wastes. as outlined in Case for Change 4.
- Generate a set of standard Waste Acceptance Criteria (WAC), standardised packages etc. for new disposal facilities in Europe as outlined in Case for Change 5. As such may incentivise cross border facilities and services.
- Secure that investments in facilities and arrangements for shared cross border facilities and services should, as outlined in the Analysis Section, in a well-defined way address
 - technical needs by the nuclear industry waste owners interested in taking benefit of cross border treatment.
 - regulatory requirements of the involved authorities.
 - environmental protection and sustainability aspects.
 - commercial and operational aspects related to the cross-border facilities including facility utilisation, economy of scale, full life cycle cost and financial risks.
 - political and sociopolitical expectations including reduction of the stock of untreated radioactive waste, shorter decommissioning projects, safe transports and handling and loss of local jobs.

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5.3 Circular economy – Business case

We present business cases for potential strategies for the implementation of circular economy principles in nuclear decommissioning. These strategies have been informed by case studies from HARPERS project partners. These solutions are not mutually exclusive, and some can be implemented in combination to maximize ecological, financial, and societal benefits.

5.3.1 Problem statement and Case for Change

Alignment with European Commission objectives/priorities

Sustainable development is a core principle of the Treaty on European Union (EU) and a priority objective for the EU's internal and external policies. In line with this, the European Commission adopted a new circular economy action plan (CEAP) in March 2020 which emphasises waste reduction.

The linear approach to nuclear decommissioning, where facilities and materials are disposed of following their first use rather than reused or recycled, generates substantial amounts of waste. The nuclear industry can significantly reduce the volume of waste generated by adopting circular economy principles—such as recycling, repurposing, and minimizing resource use. Adopting these principles would align the nuclear decommissioning industry with European objectives as well as lessening the environmental impact of disposal and conserving valuable resources, contributing to broader ecological sustainability.

Harmonizing practices, regulations, and standards across Europe is also a key objective of the European Commission, fostering consistency and cooperation among member states. The drive towards implementation of circular economy principles can also aid efforts to implement harmonising measures as international collaborative work is crucial to effective implementation of circular economy principles within the nuclear decommissioning sector. Therefore, a unified approach to these practices can enhance efficiency, reduce barriers to cross-border initiatives, and support compliance with EU-wide sustainability goals. This coordinated effort would not only strengthen

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alignment with the EU's CEAP but also reinforce the overall sustainability of the nuclear decommissioning process across Europe.

Customer user needs – current and future

Implementing circular economy practices in the nuclear industry can help optimise the use of disposal capacity in repositories with limited capacity, ensuring future waste management needs are met efficiently. By reducing the volume of waste, the industry can decrease reliance on specialised disposal facilities, which may be costly and resource intensive. Additionally, reusing and recycling materials minimizes the need for new resource acquisition, supporting long-term operational efficiency.

Societal expectations for sustainability and circular economy practices are rising across all industries, including the nuclear sector. As a result, stakeholder demands, particularly from civil society, are a key driver in the adoption of circular economy principles within the industry. Embracing circular economy principles has the potential to position the nuclear industry as a leader in sustainability, improving its public image and promoting societal acceptance.

However, regulatory complexity and fragmentation across jurisdictions, differing practices and inconsistent standards can hinder the adoption of circular economy principles. Addressing these inconsistencies, and harmonising practices, regulations and standards, is essential to enable adoption of circular economy principles and to meeting both current and future customer needs.

5.3.2 Business cases

Four Business cases were assessed:

- On-site disposal (OSD) of concrete
- Recycling of concrete,
- Recycling of steel
- Recycling of copper and aluminium.

These business cases were assessed against a common baseline of near surface disposal at a low lever waste disposal facility. The assessment consists of comparative

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analysis against the T-E-C-O-P attributes with red-amber-green (RAG) coding used to compare each BC against the baseline approach.

5.3.2.1 Business case 1 - On-site disposal of concrete

Current Proposal

Lightly contaminated or activated concrete may be disposed of on-site in a manner more consistent with the implementation of circular economy principles than the baseline. This approach is being implemented by the UK's Nuclear Restoration Services (NRS) in the decommissioning of the Magnox-type power plant at Trawsfynydd. NRS is currently seeking regulatory approval for the implementation of on-site disposal (OSD) involving both *in-situ* disposal (ISD) and disposal for a purpose (DFAP). Redundant radioactive structures located below the demolition cutline are to be disposed of *in-situ* and radioactive demolition arisings, generated through demolition of concrete and masonry structures located above the demolition cutline, are used to infill unwanted voids.

The opportunity to take advantage of on-site disposal in the UK would not be possible without regulatory guidance on the release of nuclear sites from environmental regulations (the "Guidance on Requirements for Release" or GRR), which was published by the UK environment agencies in 2018. In order to take advantage of many other opportunities for onsite disposal, similar, harmonised guidance should be developed by other countries based on the same basic principles of environmental protection.

Benefits and Risks

The advantages of this approach over the traditional linear economy baseline include the reuse of materials that would otherwise require off-site disposal, reducing the burden on the Low Level Waste Repository (LLWR) and other facilities with limited capacity. It also reduces material requirements by reusing radioactive material as bulk void infill, avoiding the need to import non-radioactive filler materials. Additionally, this strategy minimizes the number of heavy goods vehicle (HGV) movements, significantly reducing transportation costs and the associated environmental impact. The reduction

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in the number of HGV movements was also viewed as a significant benefit by the local community. This approach is also applicable to both activated and contaminated concrete.

However, the volume of concrete which can be disposed of in this manner may be constrained by the volume of below ground voids which require infilling. At co-located facilities (i.e., those with 'A' and 'B' reactors), it may be possible to mitigate this constraint by redistributing waste concrete between the two sites, allowing for more efficient use of available void space. Additionally, coordinating the timing and volume of disposal activities across both facilities may further optimize the infilling process and allow for the sharing of facilities, equipment and expertise.

5.3.2.2 Business case 2 - Recycling of concrete,

Current proposal

Lightly contaminated or activated concrete may be recycled for use as an aggregate or supplementary cementitious material (SCM) in new concrete. ENGIE, in Belgium, is currently conducting a research and development project to investigate opportunities for recycling conditionally cleared concrete.

Contaminated concrete may be pre-treated by scabbling or other related methods which remove the contaminated surface layer to decrease the average specific activity. This widens the range of concrete sources for which recycling may be a viable disposal route. However, this approach is not suitable for activated concrete.

Further harmonization of criteria for conditional clearance of concrete demolition arisings would allow this opportunity to be implemented more widely in Europe.

Benefits and risks

Recycling concrete can lead to cost savings and reduces the demand for disposal space in repositories. Moreover, producing new concrete is CO₂ intensive (concrete production accounts for approximately 6 to 10% of global CO₂ emissions attributed to human activity). Using low carbon concrete helps to decrease the environmental impact. Low carbon concrete uses larger amounts of SCM than conventional concrete, and recycled concrete, if appropriately prepared, can serve as the SCM.

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However, there are challenges associated with this approach. The use of crushed concrete as an aggregate is relatively new and still in the process of optimization. Additionally, there may be stakeholder concerns regarding the use of recycled concrete outside of the nuclear industry if it is perceived to still be radioactive. In Sweden it has been found that these concerns can be addressed with effective and early stakeholder communication. However, the effectiveness of such communication varies internationally in line with public perceptions of the nuclear industry and trust in public institutions. It is also possible to assuage the concerns of stakeholders by reusing the recycled concrete within the nuclear industry and thus Engie's project is focused on these opportunities.

The activity limits on concrete destined for release are very stringent even if conditional clearance is employed. Furthermore, in some regulatory frameworks, conditional clearance means that each release requires a specific license, along with a thorough dose impact assessment as part of the approval process.

5.3.2.3 Business case 3 - Recycling of steel

Current proposal

Recycling of steel from decommissioned nuclear facilities offers a significant opportunity to implement circular economy principles, reducing waste and conserving valuable materials. Such recycling is already an established practise in facilities such as those run by Cyclife at Nyköping in Sweden, Siempelkamp in Germany, JAVYS in Slovakia and Centraco in France, as well as in planned facilities such as Technocentre in France.

The steel is melted in an induction furnace into metal ingots suitable for clearance (either general or specific) so that they can be used in conventional or nuclear activity. Melting in induction furnaces homogenizes the metal and ensures the transfer of certain key nuclides from the metal to the slag, or to the off-gas filters while it densifies the material. Samples of the molten metal are taken after slag removal to demonstrate that clearance levels have been achieved.

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Metal decontamination, via chemical or mechanical means, is typically conducted prior to melting, and in some states (e.g., Sweden) is a regulatory requirement. This allows a wider range of activities of contaminated steels to be accepted. However, decontamination is ineffective for activated materials and thus only steels which have experienced only minor amounts of activation are suitable for melting.

It is possible to process steel which would not be suitable for clearance after decontamination and melting) in a metal melting facility but the process either only functions as a size reduction process, or the output is limited to uses within the nuclear industry such as in disposal containers⁶.

Steel recycling facilities are large and complex, requiring substantial capital investment. In many countries, the inventory of radioactive steel does not justify developing a dedicated recycling facility. Therefore, a collaborative, cross-border approach is necessary, allowing multiple countries to use a shared facility, even if it is ultimately owned by one nation. This approach would be significantly facilitated by the harmonization of regulations, practices, and standards.

Benefits and risks

The benefits of this approach are substantial. Recycling steel reduces the demand for new raw materials, conserves space in disposal repositories, and mitigates the environmental impact of steel production, which is traditionally CO₂-intensive. However, there may be stakeholder concerns regarding the use of recycled steel, which is perceived to be radioactive by some sectors of society, outside the nuclear industry. In Sweden, effective stakeholder communication has overcome these potential concerns which means that 100% of the metal ingots generated by Cyclife Sweden and released without conditions are sold to the conventional metal industry for manufacturing of new products for the public domain. However, the effectiveness of such risk communication varies internationally in line with public perceptions of the nuclear industry and trust in public institutions.

⁶ This is an illustrative example that is not currently in use.

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5.3.2.4 Business case 4 - Recycling of Copper and Aluminium cables

Current proposal

In the Orcade project, which is part of the Plan d'Investissements d'Avenir, Andra is attempting to develop a facility for separating the components of electrical cables, a radioactivity-free metal core and a peripheral polymer sheath with potential surface contamination, which does not transfer contamination from the sheath to the underlying metal. The metals (copper, aluminium) could then be recycled, and the sheath may be suitable for size reduction by incineration. It is also possible to recycle electrical cables by decontaminating them prior to stripping, although this process may be more sensitive to the nature and quantity of contamination. This is an established practice which in Germany has successfully processed more than 200 tonnes of contaminated cables.

Recycling of other types of waste copper, brass and aluminium is standard practice and implemented by Cyclife and other organisations.

In many countries, the inventory of radioactively contaminated cables does not justify developing a dedicated recycling facility. Therefore, a collaborative, cross-border approach is likely to be needed, allowing multiple countries to use a shared facility, even if it is ultimately owned by one nation. This approach would be significantly facilitated by the harmonization of regulations, practices, and standards.

Benefits and risks

The primary benefit of this approach is to reduce the demand for new copper and aluminium production by energy-intensive processes associated with significant carbon emissions. Additionally, the recycling process reduces the volume of waste that must be consigned to repositories. Initial calculations by the Orcade project teams estimate that electrical cables account for 10% by volume (or 3% by mass) of the dismantling waste to be managed.

However, whilst wire separation into polymer and metal components is an established practise for inactive cables; whether this can be done without contaminating the metal core remains an active area of research. Additionally, there may be stakeholder

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concerns regarding the wider use of recycled metals from the nuclear industry in other industries.

5.3.2.5 Comparative analysis

Table 8 presents a comparative analysis of the technologies presented in the business case sections against a baseline of disposal in a dedicated facility using a T-E-C-O-P approach. This analysis is conducted using a “red-amber-green” (RAG) approach where red signifies that the technology is significantly worse than the baseline, amber that it is about the same and green that it is significantly better than the baseline. In this analysis, it is assumed that recycling of a material means that an equivalent amount of ‘new’ material does not need to be mined and processed.

The analysis clearly indicates that all four technologies outperform the baseline of direct disposal, with environmental and commercial considerations being the primary drivers for their implementation. However, the additional complexity of these technologies, compared to the baseline, results in lower performance in the technical category. Despite this, these technical challenges do not present insurmountable barriers to implementation. International collaboration and sharing of facilities between member states would aid the surmounting of these challenges (for example, characterisation facilities may be complex, highly specialised, and face limited demand, so it may be advantageous for member states to share them). Such collaboration would be facilitated by harmonised regulations, practices, and standards.

Table 8: Comparative TECOP analysis for Technologies presented in the circular economy business case descriptions.

Category	Sub-category	On-Site Disposal of Concrete	Recycling of Concrete	Recycling of Steel	Recycling of Copper and Aluminium Cables
Technical	Operability (complexity)	Techniques for demolition of very large infrastructure must be developed on a case-by-case basis but does use existing technology (this affects both base case and variant). Does not require digging out foundations which base case does.	Recycling of concrete requires higher standards of characterisation than the baseline, which can be difficult, especially for activated concrete. Techniques for demolition of very large complexes needs to be developed on a case-by-case basis but do use existing technology (this affects both base case and variant). Concrete requires crushing and grading in order to be used as aggregate.	Melting steel into ingots is a relatively simple process but pre-treatment decontamination is more complex. If required, reuse as packaging (or other bespoke nuclear infrastructure) would also increase complexity.	Stripping of electrical cable insulation is an established process, but doing this without contaminating the underlying metal is more challenging.
	Flexibility	Flexible to range of concrete types but more characterisation is required for more complicated or contaminated structures to determine suitability. Could be more flexible than baseline as can pick and choose what to leave/remove.	Flexible to range of concrete types but limited maximum acceptable activity.	Some sensitivity to different alloy types. Issues around characterisation and acceptability of bulk activated metals and sensitive to inventory of long-lived activation products.	Flexible to a range of wire and cable types
Environmental	Raw Material Requirements	Diversion of waste from dedicated disposal facility reduces the demands of said facility as it reduces the overall facility size required. Avoids use of aggregate from off-site	Diversion of waste from dedicated disposal facility reduces the demands of said facility as it reduces the overall facility size required but requires (relatively fewer) resources for reprocessing. Reduces requirements for 'new' concrete aggregate	Diversion of waste from dedicated disposal facility reduces the demands of said facility as it reduces the overall facility size required but requires (relatively fewer) resources for reprocessing. Reduces requirements for 'new' steel	Diversion of waste from dedicated disposal facility reduces the demands of said facility as it reduces the overall facility size required but requires (relatively fewer) resources for reprocessing. Reduces requirements for 'new' copper and aluminium
	Energy Consumption	Reduced demand for disposal facility Reduced transport requirements	Reduced demand for disposal facility Roughly comparable energy use between converting concrete to aggregate and creating new aggregate	Reduced demand for disposal facility Recycling of steel is less energy intensive than creating 'new' steel	Reduced demand for disposal facility Recycling of copper and aluminium is less energy intensive than creating 'new' copper and aluminium
	Carbon Footprint	Reduced transport requirements and disposal facility demand	Reduced disposal facility demand	Reduced disposal facility and creation of 'new' steel has a larger carbon footprint than recycling of steel.	Reduced disposal facility demand and creation of 'new' copper or aluminium has a larger carbon footprint than recycling of steel.
	Environmental Impact (Rad and non-rad)	Radiological environmental impacts would be very low and be in compliance with relevant regulatory criteria. Avoid emission of NO _x associated with HGV movements.	Radiological environmental impacts would be very low and be compliant with relevant regulatory criteria.	Radiological environmental impacts would be very low and be compliant with relevant regulatory criteria. Avoids environmental impacts of mining new ore (e.g., potential release of hazardous substances).	Radiological environmental impacts would be very low and be compliant with relevant regulatory criteria. Avoids environmental impacts of mining new ore (e.g., potential release of hazardous substances) .

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Category	Sub-category	On-Site Disposal of Concrete	Recycling of Concrete	Recycling of Steel	Recycling of Copper and Aluminium Cables
	Secondary waste generation	Negligible.	Negligible.	Slag and decontamination products, but overall lower total volume of waste than baseline.	Cable insulation, but overall lower total volume of waste than baseline
	Waste Hierarchy Compliance	Some re-use to fill voids and diversion of waste away from disposal facility.	Recycling	Recycling	Recycling
Commercial	Lifecycle Cost / Benefit	Reduced construction (foundations left <i>in-situ</i>) and transport requirements and disposal facility demand	Reduced disposal facility demand and generation of a material with value.	Reduced disposal facility demand and generation of a material with value.	Reduced disposal facility demand and generation of a material with value.
	Size of opportunity	Very large	Very large (but smaller than OSD) Aggregate specifications within the nuclear industry are often strict which can limit applicability.	Very large	Very large
	Cost contingency / risk	Any OSD has to be balanced against the implications for the whole site. Leaving waste on site leads to risks at site continuing for longer – either because the site remains open for longer or during a post-closure monitoring period.	Process must be appropriately scaled to the opportunity available at a particular site (mismatch of predicted and actual inventories suitable for process).	Relatively small.	Relatively small
Operational	Workforce requirements	Potentially greater characterisation requirements but fewer construction and transport requirements	Greater characterisation requirements	Greater characterisation requirements	Relatively little difference
	Operational Safety	Avoids having to remove large volumes of below-ground structural concrete. Less road transport and waste handling.	Avoids operational safety risks of quarrying new aggregate. Crushing of recycled concrete slightly higher risk than new aggregate due to potential release of radioactive dust.	Size reduction is required either way. Avoids operational safety risks of mining and processing new ore.	Avoids operational safety risks of mining and processing new ore.
(Socio)Political	Regulatory Compliance	Not assessed here – however, all processes would benefit from harmonization of regulations (e.g. regarding clearance levels, characterization requirements, acceptance criteria for disposal, recycling) and cross-boundary shipment of wastes to shared facilities			
	Wider Public Perception	Limited wider interest	Potential concern around 'traceability' if recycled material is used outside the nuclear industry. This has not been an issue for release of recycled steel in Sweden but may be an issue elsewhere.	Potential concern around 'traceability' if recycled material is used outside the nuclear industry. This has not been an issue for release of recycled steel in Sweden but may be an issue elsewhere.	Potential concern around 'traceability' if recycled material is used outside the nuclear industry. This has not been an issue for release of recycled steel in Sweden but may be an issue elsewhere.
	Local Public Perception	In the case study provided the local public are generally in favour because of the reduction in HGV movements.	Generally in favour but depends on location of recycling facility and balance of local traffic.	In the case study provided the local public are in favour. However, local public perceptions are likely to vary significantly	Generally in favour but depends on location of recycling facility and balance of local traffic.

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Category	Sub-category	On-Site Disposal of Concrete	Recycling of Concrete	Recycling of Steel	Recycling of Copper and Aluminium Cables
		However, local public perceptions are likely to vary significantly between sites depending upon site-specific local factors.		between sites depending upon site-specific local factors.	

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5.3.3 Recommendations

This business case report evaluates four recycling and disposal technologies—on-site disposal of concrete, recycling of concrete, steel, and copper/aluminium—against a baseline of direct disposal in a dedicated facility. Using a T-E-C-O-P analysis (Technical, Environmental, Commercial, Operational, and (Socio)Political), each technology's alignment with circular economy principles is analysed, assessing its potential to reduce environmental impact, improve resource efficiency, and support sustainable nuclear decommissioning.

The analysis finds that each technology offers significant environmental and commercial benefits compared to the baseline, primarily through reduced resource demand, lower energy use, and minimised carbon emissions. However, these technologies also have some challenges, particularly in the technical category, where the need for extensive and detailed characterisation represents a notable challenge. The identified challenges are by no means insurmountable, particularly if an internationally collaborative approach is adopted. Such collaboration would both drive and benefit from the harmonisation of practices and standards across countries. Indeed, all of the technologies and processes discussed would benefit from harmonization of regulations (e.g. regarding clearance levels, characterization requirements, acceptance criteria for disposal, recycling) and cross-border shipment of wastes to shared facilities.

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5.4 Advanced Technology – Business Case

The adoption of advanced technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), digitalisation, robotics, and related innovations, is transforming the back-end of the nuclear facility lifecycle. These technologies hold the potential to enhance operational efficiency, improve safety, and achieve long-term cost savings in areas such as decommissioning, waste management, and environmental restoration. Innovations like digital twins, autonomous systems, and advanced data analytics provide opportunities to optimise processes, reduce risks, and support better decision-making. Developing a business case for these technologies involves more than just demonstrating cost efficiencies. It requires a comprehensive evaluation of their strategic, economic, operational and sustainability impacts. Using a structured framework, such as the Five Case Model, allows for a detailed analysis across the following dimensions:

- **Strategic:** Aligning the adoption of these technologies with overarching goals such as improved safety, regulatory compliance, and operational modernisation.
- **Economic:** Demonstrating public value through enhanced safety, sustainability, and cost-effectiveness.
- **Commercial:** Addressing market readiness and ensuring alignment with industry trends to encourage successful implementation.
- **Financial:** Assessing affordability and long-term value, balancing up-front investments with potential savings.
- **Management:** Establishing robust project delivery mechanisms, regulatory compliance, and workforce readiness to maximise impact.

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Figure 1. The Five Case Model for Evaluating the Economic Case for Advanced Technologies in the Nuclear Back-End

5.4.1 Problem statement – need for change

The nuclear back-end - encompassing decommissioning, dismantling, waste management, and environmental restoration - faces systemic challenges that hinder safety, efficiency, and sustainability. These issues underscore the critical need for change and justify the adoption of innovative technologies.

Decontamination and Waste Management Inefficiencies

Current practices in decontamination are limited to a select number of methodologies (e.g. concrete scabbling, water jet washing, grid blasting etc.) which are commonly applied at the final stages of dismantling decommissioning. In contrast, potential benefits could be realised if advanced, standardised technologies were used at an earlier phase of the nuclear facility lifecycle. Key challenges include:

- Some methods for decontamination result in higher volumes of (secondary) waste, increasing financial and environmental burdens.
- Inefficiencies in handling and processing diverse waste streams due to non-optimised waste treatment technologies.
- Inconsistent qualification and testing processes across jurisdictions, delaying the adoption of effective technologies.

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These inefficiencies result in significant cost overruns, delays, and operational challenges, while also putting additional strain on the available free repository volumes. Harmonised approaches to technology assessment and qualification are urgently needed to streamline processes, reduce waste volumes, and improve overall sustainability.

Barriers to Robotics and Automation Adoption

Despite their potential to transform operations, robotics and automation adoption in the nuclear back-end remains limited. Key issues include:

- Reliability challenges for robotic systems operating in high-radiation environments.
- High costs of development and deployment, particularly for modular and adaptable systems.
- Regulatory frameworks lagging behind technological advances, creating uncertainty around compliance and discouraging investment.
- Reluctance among operators to adopt first-of-a-kind technologies, preferring proven solutions.

These barriers result in continued reliance on manual processes, increasing risks to personnel and limiting efficiency. Standardising protocols and fostering regulatory approach and application alignment can overcome these challenges and unlock the full potential of robotics in decommissioning and waste management.

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Underutilisation of Digital Twin and BIM Technologies

DT and advanced BIM technologies offer significant opportunities to enhance planning, decision-making, and risk management. However, their adoption has been hindered by:

- Interoperability issues between software platforms and hardware systems.
- Cybersecurity concerns related to the protection of sensitive data and systems.
- Lack of standardised certification frameworks, limiting scalability and integration.

Addressing these barriers can enable organisations to harness the full potential of DT and BIM technologies, improving operational efficiency, resource optimisation, and safety outcomes.

Regulatory and Organisational Challenges

The nuclear back-end operates under stringent regulatory frameworks that can hinder the early adoption of innovative technologies. Implementation and demonstration of advanced technologies also requires consensus between multi-discipline stakeholders (technology developer, site licence owner, waste owner, waste repository, regulators etc.), commonly spread across different organisations with different drivers and practices. Key challenges include:

- Time-consuming and costly compliance processes, delaying technology implementation.
- Varied regulatory approaches between countries and organisational procedures across jurisdictions, create inconsistencies and inefficiencies in adopting disruptive technologies.

By providing standardised approaches to technology assessment and qualification and by facilitating the exchange of practical experiences and good practices across multi-discipline organisations and jurisdictions some of these constraints can be alleviated.

These efforts can accelerate the adoption of advanced technologies, reduce uncertainty, and foster collaboration across the nuclear sector.

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Economic Pressures and Sustainability Goals

Decommissioning and, in general, waste management projects are characterised by high costs and extended timelines, creating significant economic pressures. Simultaneously, there is increasing demand for these activities to align with sustainability goals, like:

- Minimising environmental impact,
- Reducing waste generation, and
- Optimising resource use.

Balancing these competing priorities requires innovative, cost-effective, acceptable and environmentally sustainable solutions. However, technical, organisational, and regulatory barriers have hindered the adoption of such approaches. Addressing these barriers through harmonised standards and international collaboration is essential to achieve meaningful progress.

5.4.2 The HARPERS Economic Case Framework

A structured framework is proposed for developing Business Cases for emerging technologies which assesses the economic feasibility of new approaches in the nuclear back-end by comparing them against the current baseline.

This proposed framework is then utilized to perform the basic analysis for the three key areas studied in detail as a starting point to develop economic business cases.

The framework exists of following steps (Figure 4):

1. Baseline Analysis:

Identify the needs, issues, and gaps in current practices. This baseline serves as a reference point for evaluating alternative approaches and highlights urgency.

2. Change Scenarios:

Introduce multiple change scenarios (e.g., Scenario 1, Scenario 2, Scenario 3 in the figure below), each representing a different strategy to address baseline issues. These scenarios are evaluated for their ability to meet needs and resolve gaps effectively.

3. Scenario Assessment:

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Assess each scenario for its aims, net benefits, and required steps to advance the business case. This stage provides a clear evaluation of how each scenario compares to the baseline in addressing identified challenges.

4. Decision Point:

Determine whether to continue developing a detailed business case for one or more of the scenarios based on their potential net benefits and alignment with project goals.

Figure 4: The proposed HARPERS Economic Case Framework for advanced Technologies

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To assess the value and the feasibility of the proposed innovation compared to baseline practices, a 4-step approach is recommended (Figure 5):

1. **Identify Key Attributes:**

Define essential attributes using the T-E-C-O-P dimensions for a thorough evaluation:

- Technical: Factors such as operability, maintainability, reliability, and overall system performance.
- Economic: Aspects including costs, potential savings, lifecycle value, and long-term financial benefits.
- Commercial: Attributes like market readiness, scalability, adaptability, and alignment with industry demand.
- Organisational: Considerations such as workforce readiness, operational efficiency, resource allocation, and capacity building.
- Socio-Political: Elements including regulatory compliance, public acceptance, societal impact, and alignment with sustainability goals.

2. **Analyse Impacts and Risks:**

Compare baseline and proposed approaches to evaluate:

- Impacts: Benefits and opportunities across TECOP dimensions.
- Risks: Dependencies, constraints, and sensitivities affecting outcomes.

3. **Compare Options:**

Perform a detailed comparison of scenarios across the following four categories, building on the analysis of attributes identified within the T-E-C-O-P dimensions. The examples under each category illustrate potential focus areas for evaluation:

- Safety: Consider aspects such as radiation protection, personnel safety, contamination control, and environmental impact mitigation. These examples highlight how attributes primarily related to the Technical and Organisational dimensions of T-E-C-O-P might improve safety outcomes.
- Cost: Evaluate lifecycle costs, including examples like upfront investments, operational expenses, potential savings (both short and long term), and long-term financial sustainability. These considerations draw mainly on attributes within the Economic and Commercial dimensions of T-E-C-O-P.
- Time: Assess implementation timelines, including examples such as project duration, regulatory buy-in and approval processes, and potential delays. This category relates largely to dependencies and constraints identified in the Organisational and Technical dimensions.

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- Risks/Feasibility/Sustainability: Analyse potential risks and implementation challenges, referencing examples like technical, regulatory, and organisational hurdles. Use this step to evaluate feasibility, alignment with sustainability goals, and potential for long-term success, as informed by all dimensions of T-E-C-O-P.

4. Make a Decision:

Consolidate findings to decide whether to advance a scenario to the next stage of business case development. Assess net benefits and alignment with project objectives.

Figure 5: Practical implementation of the proposed framework for developing an economic business case for advanced technologies.

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5.4.3 Economic case for advanced technologies

This section examines the challenges and opportunities associated with standardising innovative technologies in the nuclear back-end. It focuses on three key areas: i) innovative decontamination, environmental restoration, waste treatment and immobilisation technologies; ii) robotics and automation; and iii) DT and advanced BIM technologies. Developing a generic business case for the standardisation of these technologies, even at a high level (such as the Economic Case), is inherently complex. These complexities stem from significant variations in expected return on investment (ROI) and associated risks, which are influenced by factors such as site-specific conditions, the regulatory approach and operational environment of the country, and the type of technology being adopted.

The applicability of the proposed framework was tested by applying it to the 3 key areas. The aim was to demonstrate the useability of the Framework. The outcome can be used as a starting point for further elaboration towards an economic case.

For each of the three focus areas, the following provides:

- A short summary of the motivation (need) for technology adoption.
- A high-level T-E-C-O-P analysis.
- Guidance for rating and comparing technology options against the baseline and with each other, to support decisions on whether to advance the business case.

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5.4.3.1 Innovative Waste Management and Decontamination Technologies

Need for standardising approaches to technology assessment and qualification for decontamination, environmental restoration, waste treatment and immobilisation

Some decontamination processes and waste treatments are limited by inconsistent standards across sites and countries, leading to inefficiencies and increased costs. Some of these methods generate significant secondary waste and require extensive regulatory approvals. Standardising technology assessment and qualification can streamline processes, align practices with regulatory requirements and suggested good practice, and reduce the costs and time associated with adopting new technologies. Innovations such as volume reduction technologies and waste stabilisation techniques can significantly improve safety and sustainability.

T-E-C-O-P analysis

Technical

- **Opportunities:**
 - Establishing standardised qualification processes improves reliability and scalability for innovative decontamination and waste treatment technologies.
 - Promotes the adoption of volume reduction and stabilisation techniques.
- **Barriers:**
 - Some methods lack field-proven frameworks to evaluate and integrate new technologies effectively.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Success relies on advancements in testing methods and material handling standards in close European and international cooperation.

Economic

- **Opportunities:**
 - Standardisation reduces waste processing costs and lifecycle expenditures.
 - Pooled resources for research and development streamline innovation and reduce upfront costs.
- **Barriers:**
 - Initial investment costs create financial risks for stakeholders.
- **Sensitivity:**
 - Financial success depends on robust cost-benefit analyses and consistent waste volume reduction metrics.

Commercial

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- **Opportunities:**
 - Expands markets by harmonising waste treatment protocols and creating a common standard for waste classification.
 - Encourages partnerships among technology providers and operators.
- **Barriers:**
 - Resistance to adopting novel methods due to perceived market uncertainties.
 - Poor user experience or inadequate engagement with end-users.

Organisational

- **Opportunities:**
 - Enhanced collaboration through unified waste management standards.
 - Reduced operational silos by providing structured frameworks for technology integration.
- **Barriers**
 - Employee reluctance to shift from established processes.
 - Absence of advocacy from senior management.

(Socio-)Political

- **Opportunities:**
 - Builds public trust through environmentally responsible waste management practices.
 - Aligns with policy goals for sustainability and environmental protection.
- **Barriers:**
 - Resistance from local communities regarding new waste management facilities.
 - Workforce displacement concerns due to higher automation or unequal access to training and technology.

Guidance for rating and comparison (checklist)

Safety

- **Impacts:**
 - Reduction in radiation exposure for personnel.
 - Better contamination control and environmental impact mitigation.
 - Improved safety through waste stabilisation.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Regulatory requirements and alignment with safety standards.
 - Advancements in monitoring and safety equipment technologies.
- **Constraints:**
 - Costs associated with updating safety measures to new technology.
 - Skilled workforce availability for handling innovative technologies.

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Cost

- **Impacts:**
 - Reduction in waste processing and lifecycle costs.
 - Improved cost-effectiveness in decontamination processes.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Access to government funding and subsidies.
 - Market demand for decontamination services.
 - Shared resources for technology development.
- **Constraints:**
 - Limited budget allocations for innovation.
 - Competition for financial resources.

Time

- **Impacts:**
 - Faster project timelines through improved processes.
 - Reduced delays in waste processing.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Streamlined regulatory approvals for innovative technologies.
 - Technological readiness for deployment.
- **Constraints:**
 - Complex regulatory environments leading to delays.

Risks/Feasibility/Sustainability

- ▲⁷ Long-term waste stabilisation enhances sustainability.
- ▲ Resource efficiency in decontamination processes reduces environmental impact.
- ▼⁸ Limited options for sustainable waste disposal create challenges.
- ▼ Balancing cost and sustainability goals is difficult.
- ▼ Organizational scepticism regarding new technologies may hinder adoption.
- ▲ Collaboration between stakeholders increases chances of successful implementation.

⁷ Up-oriented triangle: signifies a positive change/ impact.

⁸ Down-oriented triangle: indicates a negative change/impact.

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5.4.3.2 Robotics and Automation

Need for standardising protocols and systems to support adoption of robotics & automation in decommissioning, dismantling and waste management

Robotics and automation are essential for reducing human exposure to hazardous environments and increasing efficiency in nuclear decommissioning. However, barriers such as a lack of universal qualification protocols, reliability concerns in high-radiation fields, and limited modularity hinder adoption. Standardisation can address these issues by providing clear frameworks for technology assessment and operational guidelines, ensuring that robotics systems are interoperable and adaptable to various tasks. This approach also fosters international collaboration and knowledge sharing.

T-E-C-O-P analysis

Technical

- **Opportunities:**
 - Standardised protocols for robotics qualification ensure operational reliability in high-radiation environments.
 - Modular designs facilitate adaptability across multiple decommissioning tasks.
- **Risks:**
 - Challenges in achieving technical robustness for consistent operation under extreme conditions.
- **Barriers:**
 - Limited field-ready robotic solutions that meet regulatory standards.
 - Challenges in integrating new technologies with existing systems.
 - Poor user experience due to inadequate training, or insufficient engagement with end-users.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Dependent on advancements in radiation shielding and robotic dexterity.

Economic

- **Opportunities:**
 - Reduced operational costs by replacing manual labour in hazardous environments.
 - Standardised qualification reduces duplicated testing expenses.
- **Barriers:**
 - Development and deployment costs for robotic systems.
- **Sensitivity:**

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- Adoption rates depend on achieving clear ROI and reducing maintenance costs.

Commercial

- **Opportunities:**

- Broadened market appeal by providing trusted, certified robotic solutions.
- Increased private-sector investment in robotics through transparent qualification standards.

- **Barriers:**

- Stakeholder hesitancy to invest in unproven robotic systems.

Organisational

- **Opportunities:**

- Structured guidelines for training staff to operate and maintain robotic systems.
- Cross-organisation sharing of robotic innovations and lessons learned.

- **Barriers:**

- Resistance from workers due to concerns about job displacement.

(Socio-)Political

- **Opportunities:**

- Enhanced worker safety by minimising human exposure to radiation.
- Demonstration of proactive adoption of innovative technologies to the public.

- **Barriers:**

- Scepticism about the reliability and safety of automated systems in critical operations.
- Complying with varying laws and standards across different countries at multinational companies.

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Guidance for rating and comparison (checklist)

Safety

- **Impacts:**
 - Reduction in radiation exposure by automating tasks in hazardous areas.
 - Minimisation of human intervention, enhancing operational safety.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Advanced robotics capable of functioning under extreme conditions.
 - Alignment with international safety standards for robotics.
- **Constraints:**
 - Development and deployment costs.
 - Skilled personnel for robotic system operations.

Cost

- **Impacts:**
 - Reduced operational costs by automating repetitive or hazardous tasks.
 - Increased cost-efficiency for large-scale decommissioning projects.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Strong cost-benefit analyses to justify investments.
 - Support from public and private stakeholders.
- **Constraints:**
 - Initial costs for development and deployment of robotic systems.

Time

- **Impacts:**
 - Accelerated project timelines through efficient robotic automation.
 - Reduced delays in decommissioning due to human limitations.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Timely deployment of qualified robotic systems.
 - Streamlined approval processes for robotic systems.
- **Constraints:**
 - Long lead times for developing and qualifying robotic systems.

Risks/Feasibility/Sustainability

- ▲ Feasibility of automating complex processes improves operational efficiency.
- ▲ Reduced long-term risks by minimising human exposure in hazardous environments.
- ▼ Limited availability of field-ready robotic solutions presents barriers to adoption.
- ▼ Organisational resistance due to workforce displacement concerns may delay implementation.
- ▼ Organizational and time-to-time regulatory scepticism about the reliability and safety of automated systems could slow progress.
- ▼ High investment costs pose feasibility challenges for large-scale deployment.

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5.4.3.3 Digital Twins (DT) and Advanced BIM Technologies

Need for standardising digital twin and advanced BIM technology and their application

The adoption of digital twins and BIM technologies is hampered by challenges in data interoperability, cybersecurity concerns, and varied regulatory approaches between countries. These technologies offer immense potential for improving planning, monitoring, and compliance in nuclear operations. Standardising data formats, certification criteria, and integration protocols can facilitate their widespread adoption, enhancing operational efficiency and sustainability while addressing public and regulatory expectations for transparency and safety.

T-E-C-O-P analysis

Technical

- **Opportunities:**
 - Improved interoperability between digital twins and legacy systems.
 - Real-time data integration for enhanced monitoring and predictive maintenance.
- **Barriers:**
 - Cybersecurity vulnerabilities pose risks to sensitive nuclear data.
 - Interoperability challenges across diverse software platforms.

Economic

- **Opportunities:**
 - Improved efficiency in resource allocation and project planning, reducing operational costs.
 - Cost savings by optimising decommissioning timelines.
- **Barriers:**
 - Costs for initial system integration and ongoing software upgrades.

Commercial

- **Opportunities:**
 - Expanded markets by demonstrating the value of real-time operational data through certified digital twin systems.
 - Enhanced partnerships between technology developers and nuclear operators.
- **Barriers:**
 - Lack of proven commercial models for scaling DT/BIM technologies across multiple facilities.

Organisational

- **Opportunities:**

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- Standardised guidelines to streamline workforce training for DT/BIM tools.
- Enhanced collaboration by integrating data across departments and stakeholders.

(Socio-)Political

- **Opportunities:**
 - Improved public confidence by enhancing transparency in nuclear operations through real-time data.
 - Alignment with regulatory requirements for enhanced safety case demonstrations.
- **Barriers:**
 - Concerns about data security and privacy may hinder public and regulatory acceptance.

Guidance for rating and comparison (checklist)

Safety

- **Impacts:**
 - Real-time data integration for safety monitoring and predictive maintenance.
 - Enhanced safety through accurate modelling and simulation.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Development of interoperable systems to ensure real-time data sharing.
 - Effective cybersecurity measures to protect sensitive nuclear data.
- **Constraints:**
 - Cybersecurity risks associated with digital platforms.
 - Costs for system integration and upgrades.

Cost

- **Impacts:**
 - Optimisation of resource allocation, reducing operational costs.
 - Cost savings by preventing equipment failures through predictive modelling.
- **Dependencies:**
 - Investments in IT infrastructure and digital twin technologies.
 - Partnerships between technology developers and operators.
- **Constraints:**
 - Initial investment and ongoing maintenance costs.

Time

- **Impacts:**
 - Shortened project timelines through efficient planning and simulation.
 - Reduced delays by integrating real-time data into workflows.
- **Dependencies:**

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- Timely integration with existing legacy systems.
- Availability of skilled personnel for operating and maintaining DT/BIM technologies.
- **Constraints:**
 - Long lead times for system implementation.

Risks/Feasibility/Sustainability

- ▲ Improves sustainability through better resource efficiency and accurate data management.
- ▲ Reduces risks by providing real-time data for informed decision-making.
- ▼ Resistance to adopting advanced technologies due to high upfront costs.
- ▼ Public and regulator concerns about data security and system reliability could delay adoption.
- ▼ Dependence on robust cybersecurity frameworks increases complexity and costs.
- ▲ Balancing data transparency with privacy requirements can enhance trust and acceptance.

5.4.4 Suggested next steps towards policy makers

The Economic Cases presented provide a generic framework for evaluating the adoption of innovative technologies in the nuclear back-end. These analyses are intended to offer high-level insights and guidance. However, more quantitative and detailed evaluations would require application to specific use-cases, with tailored assessments of site conditions, regulatory frameworks, and technological specifications. Despite the generic nature of these cases, the analyses clearly demonstrate a strong Economic Case for harmonisation in the three areas addressed:

1. Innovative decontamination, environmental restoration, waste treatment, and immobilisation technologies,
2. Robotics and automation,
3. Digital Twin (DT) and advanced BIM technologies.

Harmonisation, or better alignment in these areas is critical to overcoming key barriers such as varied regulatory approaches from country to country, inconsistent qualification standards, and interoperability challenges. Addressing these issues through more aligned standards and approaches will facilitate higher adoption rates of innovative solutions, reduce inefficiencies, and enable smoother cross-organisational

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and cross-national collaboration. Given the broad scope of these challenges, policy makers must take ownership of the harmonisation process. Their leadership is essential to developing unified frameworks that align stakeholders, streamline the ability to achieve regulatory compliance, and promote effective implementation. Specific actions include:

- Driving the establishment of international standards for qualification and assessment, robotics protocols, and data management systems.
- Facilitating collaborative working groups and establishing platforms, such as regulatory "sandboxes," to test and align innovative technologies with regulatory frameworks.
- Promoting interoperability by spearheading efforts to standardise data formats, cybersecurity protocols, and system integration practices.
- Encouraging cross-sector knowledge sharing to build trust, exchange best practices, and foster adoption.

By prioritising harmonisation and better alignment in these three areas, policy makers can help remove systemic barriers and enable transformative advancements in nuclear decommissioning and waste management. The adoption of new technologies, particularly in areas like Artificial Intelligence (AI) and automation, is often shaped by societal and organisational attitudes. Resistance can stem from concerns such as job displacement or data security. Addressing these challenges requires organisations to focus on building trust by fostering transparency about the technology's benefits, potential risks, and safeguards. Early and consistent stakeholder engagement — through consultations, workshops, and feedback mechanisms — plays a crucial role in addressing concerns, aligning expectations, and ensuring that technology implementation is inclusive, socially responsible, and aligned with organisational goals.

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